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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Denotation
2ZERO	Towards zero emission road transport
5GAA	5G Automotive Association
5G ACIA	5G Alliance for Connected Industries and Automation
5G IA	5G Infrastructure Association
AENEAS	Association for European NanoElectronics Activities
ALICE	Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	The Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation
ARTEMIS	Association for actors in Embedded Intelligent Systems within Europe
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BVME-SG	Business Validation, Models, and Ecosystems Sub-Group
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
CISPE.cloud	Cloud Infrastructure Services Providers in Europe
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DoA	Description of the Action
EBU	European Broadcasting Union
ECHalliance	European Connected Health Alliance
ECS	Electronic Components and Systems
ECSEL	The ECSEL JU, the PPP for Electronic Components and Systems
ECSO	European Cyber Security Organisation
EF ECS	European Forum for Electronic Components and Systems
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EG	Expert Group
EPoSS	The ETP on Smart Systems Integration
ERRAC	European Rail Research Advisory Council
ERTRAC	European Road Transport Research Advisory Council
ESA	European Space Agency
ETP	European Technology Platform
ETPIS	European Technology Platform on Industrial Safety
euRobotics	International non-profit association for all stakeholders in European robotics
EUTC	Europe Utility Technology Council
GA	Grant Agreement
HiPEAC	High Performance Embedded Architecture and Compilation
JU	Joint Undertaking
KDT	Key Digital Technologies
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
NEM	New European Media Initiative, the ETP dealing with Connected, Converging and Interactive Media & Creative Industries, driving the future of digital experience
NetworldEurope	The ETP for communications networks and services
NESSI	The ETP dedicated to Software, Services and Data
Photonics21	The ETP representing the European Photonics Community
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
SRIA	Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda
WG	Working Group
WP	Work package

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1 Introduction – Overall Strategy

1.1 Introduction

Deliverable 4.2 reports on the activities and achievements related to community building and outreach during the first year of the project (i.e., from 1st July 2020 to 30th June 2021). This is done by analysing the progress made in tasks 4.1 “Stakeholder engagement and community building” and 4.2 “Outreach, dissemination and exploitation”.

The focus is on the work carried out in the January - June 2021 timeframe, while Deliverable 4.1 covered and provided detailed information on the previous first semester of the project.

In addition, this document includes some ideas to improve the initial strategy for stakeholder engagement and community building as well as the communication and dissemination plan of the project.

Due to the persistence of the Covid-19 pandemic, COREnect continued to organise events online, including the 2nd COREnect ‘internal’ workshop, a public workshop and panel at the joint EuCNC & 6G Summit 2021. The meetings of the Expert Groups also took place via video calls.

The interim activities and achievements covered by this deliverable are in line with the expectations.

1.2 Stakeholder engagement and community building strategy

As recommended in Deliverable 4.1, the stakeholder engagement and community building activities in the 2nd part of the COREnect project focused on three aspects: stakeholder identification; SMEs in the COREnect ecosystem; and stakeholder engagement. The overall strategy has remained the same, as no revision or deviation has been deemed necessary, except moving to the next stage. COREnect’s agile engagement strategy picture is reminded below¹.

Figure 1: COREnect’s Agile Engagement Stakeholder Framework²

¹ For more details on the agile engagement stakeholder framework, refer to section 2.1.1 of Deliverable 4.1.

² “Sprint Qx” in Figure 1 refers to a generic time period defining each cycle. The full cycle for COREnect lasts about 6 months, as two stages have been performed in the 1st year of the project.

The main objective of the 2nd stage of the stakeholder identification was to build upon the preliminary outcome and the documents identified in D4.1, in order to progress further in identifying the most relevant stakeholders to be engaged by COREnect. The result of this work is presented in section 2.2.

The stakeholder engagement has been proceeding in strong relation with the work performed in the COREnect Expert Groups (cf. D3.2 “Report on the 2nd Expert Group Workshop”), and the outreach, dissemination and exploitation strategies, that are described in section 3.

The main mechanisms used for reaching out to the different COREnect community stakeholders have been:

- **Email campaign:** with a self-explanatory project summary for the campaign (e.g., COREnect participation at EuCNC), reinforcing the website as the first entry point. This information always summarizes the goal of the initiative, highlighting the target audience and the benefits, along with links to the articles and project’s documentation (i.e., link to Zenodo).
- **Events organization:** webinars, workshops, etc. (e.g. EuCNC & 6G Summit). Organising these types of events has been proven effective to interact and engage with the project’s communities. These types of events are also useful to gather feedback about the project.
- **Social media strategy:** a well-planned social media strategy to spread the word about the project has been proven to be a good way of maintaining the interaction with the audience and also it has turned to be a good tool to attract different types of stakeholders. It must be put in place to 1) build an online community, 2) keep the community informed about the project’s activities and 3) engaging the community.
- **Newsletters:** From the COREnect experience a newsletter strategy is very useful tool to keep the community informed and engaged with the latest news. It is also a good tool to identify the type of stakeholders that subscribe to the newsletter.

The potential role of SMEs in the (future) COREnect /B5G / 6G ecosystem(s) was only touched upon in the initial phase of the project. Further analysis has been performed, and the result is provided in section 2.3. This work is also being used in WP2 and WP3, for aspects related to SMEs.

1.3 Outreach, dissemination and exploitation strategy

Key activities and objectives of Task 4.2 “Outreach, dissemination and exploitation” include:

- Promote the COREnect community.
- Disseminate the project results to engage the relevant stakeholders.
- Increase awareness and promotion towards targeted external stakeholders, to maximise the visibility of the project, its community, and its impact on the European industry and beyond. To this aim, a public project website, COREnect social media (Twitter and LinkedIn Group), newsletters have been launched and regularly filled with updated contents.
- Prepare dissemination material for events, conferences, and workshops.
- Organise workshops to gather the community and present the project results in conjunction with EF ECS and EuCNC, which are the main annual events for the ECS and SNS communities.
- Work towards a closer relationship between the ECS and the SNS communities, mutually enriching their long-term roadmaps and paving the way to research activities bringing together actors of the two communities.

- Provide ideas for the exploitation of the expected results.

Work on this area is described in in section 3.

2 Interim Report on Stakeholder Engagement and Community Building Outreach

2.1 The current COREnect ecosystems

As stated in the initial Deliverable 4.1, COREnect decided to proceed with a distinction between the “provisioning ecosystem”, i.e., stakeholders that shall be part of the COREnect community; and the “use case ecosystem”, i.e., the external communities that will benefit from the results obtained and released by the COREnect community. This is in line with the “5G Ecosystems White Paper” currently being drafted by the Business Validation, Models, and Ecosystems Sub-Group of the 5G IA Vision and Societal Challenges Working Group, to which COREnect is contributing.

In Deliverable 4.1, COREnect had drawn initial “stakeholder pictures”, in line with the agile stakeholder engagement methodology used in the project. In the second stage, the COREnect team focused on:

- Analysing the large amount of information listed in D4.1, to extract what is relevant to COREnect;
- Interacting among COREnect partners, and with the experts involved in the COREnect Expert Groups, to better categorise the most relevant stakeholder communities;
- Considering the contribution from external experts, invited to a public consultation stressing several important aspects of importance to COREnect.

The COREnect team revised the stakeholder pictures, building up upon the work from D4.1. Many documents and reports were thoroughly analysed, and the COREnect partners added their contributions, leading to two new stakeholder pictures, describing with more details the “COREnect provisioning ecosystem” and the “COREnect use case ecosystem”.

In the process of compiling all the stakeholders, the reports and studies carried out in relation to 5G, microelectronics, semiconductors, chips, etc., focusing both on the community and its entire value chain, as well as on potential users, have been analysed. An identification by category/type was performed, in which all the stakeholders involved play an important role in the COREnect universe. From policy makers to initiatives, a “magnifying glass” was applied to the original pictures, to get the best out of each category.

This resulted in the revision of the initial stakeholder pictures, that are displayed in the following subsections. In addition, the COREnect team drafted a first version of the accompanying glossary, that is an integral part of the agile engagement stakeholder methodology mentioned above. The glossary may be found in Annex A.

2.1.1 COREnect provisioning ecosystem: the COREnect community

The COREnect community stakeholder picture has been revised as follows.

COREnect Provisioning Ecosystem: The COREnect Community

Figure 2: COREnect provisioning ecosystem stakeholder picture

2.1.2 COREnect use-case ecosystem: users of the COREnect technologies

The revised stakeholder picture for the users of COREnect technologies is shown below.

Figure 3: COREnect use-case ecosystem stakeholder picture

2.2 SMEs in the COREnect ecosystem(s)

Important note: this section is a first attempt by COREnect at defining recommendations for SMEs in relation with activities on R&I and investments required for developing European core technologies in 5G and beyond (Task 2.2), to best position SMEs in the COREnect ecosystems (Task 4.1), and later to contribute to the recommendations of the COREnect roadmap (Task 3.2). At this initial stage, the focus is mostly on the 5G/6G ecosystem as a whole. The next stage shall focus more on the COREnect ecosystems and in particular on ways to create the conditions for European champions to potentially emerge in the domain covered by COREnect, i.e., components for 6G.

2.2.1 Position of SMEs in the COREnect ecosystem

There is a trend in the 5G ecosystem to primarily position SMEs as technology users, rather than technology providers. Another feeling is that SMEs are more interested in contributing to projects with short-term results.

In the 5G domain, the trends above were illustrated e.g., in the willingness from the EC to promote more participation from SMEs in innovation actions related to the use of 5G technology, in particular with a strong recommendation to ensure at least 50% participation of SMEs in the ICT-41 call “5G innovations for verticals with third party services”. The result was satisfactory, with an SME participation of about 50% in this call. However, it is more challenging to draw conclusions, considering that the level of participation of SMEs is similar in the 5G PPP overall in RIAs and in IAs, thus showing that SMEs have participated both in technology research (RIAs) and in projects that are closer to the market and to applications (IAs). The low level of participation of SMEs in infrastructure projects (ICT-17) may prove this right, but at the same time SMEs have not participated much in automotive-oriented projects either, potentially proving this wrong.

As far as the ECS ecosystem is concerned, the situation is actually reversed. On the one hand, the “European initiative on Processors and semiconductor technologies” states that Member States “agree to [...] support the use of semiconductor in Europe and to this end, facilitate the exploitation by SMEs of advanced chip technologies in innovative products” [Joint 21], which positions SMEs as technology users. On the other hand, in the research projects which AENEAS is involved in (ECSEL, PENTA and, prior to that, CATRENE), SMEs are often technology providers, with large companies integrating those technologies in larger systems. This is further evidenced by the content of the “SME Members Directory” [AENEAS-SME], released regularly by AENEAS, which includes mostly technology-oriented SMEs.

Looking at the above, no actual conclusion may be drawn. **COREnect shall consider that SMEs are potential contributors and stakeholders both in the technology and in the (vertical) applications ecosystems.**

2.2.2 Opportunities and challenges for SMEs

One of COREnect’s main objectives is to “create the condition for one or more European champion(s) in the domain of core technology for attaining technology sovereignty in future connectivity systems”. The assumption that is made here, is that there is room in the next 10 years in the COREnect domain for the emergence of European champions.

Although, there is no assumption from COREnect as to what form such champions shall be (start-ups, spin-offs, joint ventures, new branch in an existing company...), several reports support the idea that with the development and deployment of 5G and then of 6G, opportunities shall arise for SMEs. A recent report issued jointly by the European Investment Bank (EIB) and the European Commission (EC) stresses the importance of SMEs in the context of the development and deployment of 5G [EIB21]. According to the document, “5G will enable SMEs to participate more actively in the communications ecosystem. [...] [SMEs] will play a particularly crucial role in the success of 5G by contributing to the development of 5G-based applications and technologies that support telecom networks roll-outs, delivering benefits to citizens and companies”. According to another report entitled *5G Supply Market Trends*, “there is an opportunity for new European players to enter the [5G] market”, considering that “diversification is paramount to European and American operators, which will do all they can to hurry the development of ‘new kids’” [AIT21-1].

The public consultation organised by COREnect in relation with Deliverable 2.1 “initial vision and requirement report” highlights some opportunities that SMEs could grab³, e.g., targeting a particular part of the technology or of the market value chain; forward-looking validation of next innovative advanced products (that large companies may not be keen to look at); cooperate with research organisations in the development of technology at early stage.

Another report on 5G Supply Market Trends identifies a few trends that could be beneficial to SMEs. The authors consider that “open and interoperable 5G network solutions could provide an opportunity for new players to enter the RAN market, foster vendor diversity, increase development speed and competition”, and “are paving the way for the emergence and entrance of new players in the 5G supply market” [AIT21-2]. Those new players, who may not only be start-ups or SMEs, may play a role in various markets that will be initiated or strengthened by the deployment of 5G, e.g., Open RAN, but may also include “companies with strong competencies in hardware or software development” and “new players [who] can enter the supply market at different points, e.g., baseband players [...] or software vendors”.

Specific challenges for SMEs described by the experts who responded to the COREnect consultation include, e.g., the dependence on large-scale trial / pre-commercial infrastructures to test their products and solutions. This challenge was already identified in the 5G PPP and by the SME Working Group, and has already been addressed with various levels of success (when it comes to SME involvement) in the Phase 3 of the 5G PPP. It is planned to be addressed further in the SNS Partnership. Other experts stress that IPR and patent, and of the heavy investment required to contribute to standardisation organisations, are a hurdle for most SMEs. Some experts just consider that the market addressed by COREnect is just ‘out of reach’ for most SMEs, considering the high upfront chip development costs.

Another challenge is the fact that the single market is still not a reality in the world of telecommunications, that is still very much nation-oriented in Europe, making very challenging for small and medium-sized companies to broaden their market within the EU.

COREnect should consider as potential future “European champions” start-ups and SMEs that are able to emerge in technology, as well as in the field of (vertical) applications -but should not look only at start-ups and SMEs.

³ COREnect organised a public consultation to get feedback from experts regarding various topics related to the objectives of the project.

2.2.3 Recommendations for SMEs

When it comes to SMEs, recommendations fall mainly into three main categories:

1. Recommendations promoting the role of SMEs in the ecosystem
2. Recommendations only for SMEs
3. General recommendations applicable to SMEs

2.2.3.1 Recommendations promoting the role of SMEs in the ecosystem

Strengthening the interaction between corporate companies, research organisations, and SMEs, is one of the options that shall be considered by COREnect, to gather the best researchers in the field and ensure that Europe will be at the edge of components for 6G. The US semiconductor industry is in line with this idea, when they highlight “guiding a (r)evolution of cooperative academic, industry and government research programs” as one of their key priorities “to ensure sustainable growth for semiconductor and ICT industries” [SRC21]. This is also consistent with the proposal from the EU Commissioner for Research Mariya Gabriel, who stressed that “[forming] networks and facilitate communication between different stakeholders and start-ups” is one of the critical issues behind the creation of a European Innovation Area (EIA) [GABRIEL20]. To achieve this, she proposes to “enable matchmaking opportunities between start-ups and larger established companies”, but also to strengthen the link between innovators and entrepreneurs, and between education and innovation.

COREnect could enable matchmaking between European SMEs and other European stakeholders, covering technology, innovation, education, as well as finance and funding, in the field addressed. This shall not be limited to start-ups. The 5G PPP, as well as the ECS related programmes ECSEL and PENTA, show that all types of SMEs are contributing to innovation, whether start-ups, spin-offs, or already established SMEs. This also seems to be the goal of the future French Presidency of the EU, which is emphasizing support to high growth companies, with the initiative to overcome the issue of Europe not succeeding in creating companies worth hundreds of billions of euros like what is being achieved in the US and in China [FR21].

To support this recommendation, one of COREnect’s main objectives is to identify the relevant European stakeholders from both the microelectronics and the telecommunications ecosystem, and support building up the “COREnect community” that shall develop components for 6G, thus ensuring a better sovereignty of Europe, not only for 5G and 6G, but also in the vertical sectors that will more and more heavily depend on those technologies.

One of the key challenges that should be considered, is to find out how such a community could work together in the most effective manner, to achieve the objectives mentioned above.

The public consultation organised by COREnect in relation with Deliverable 2.1 “initial vision and requirement report”, provides some insights into possible recommendations in relation with SMEs. Overall, several experts recommend to focus on existing European strengths (e.g., software and applications, but also devices used in specific industrial sectors rather than on the consumer market), chipset design. They also suggest to strengthen the cooperation between players from the telecommunications and microelectronics domains, to organise an ecosystem that would bring the highest value to Europe. There is a high expectation that public authorities, and also somewhat that large industry, should support a balanced cooperation between large industry, SMEs, and research organisations, e.g., for critical technologies, across different technology sectors, to stimulate innovation. This could take the form of a

multi-company, or rather multi-stakeholder alliance on European technology leadership. **Strengthening the cooperation between all actors and especially research institutions, large companies, and SMEs, is a key highlight of the recommendations from the consultation. Cooperation among SMEs should also be supported.**

When it comes to the dependence on large-scale trial / pre-commercial infrastructures to test SME products and solutions, experts recommend that **public authorities should encourage a more balanced collaboration between large industry, SMEs, and research institutions**, to overcome this issue, for the benefit of Europe. SMEs and industry could cooperate more efficiently towards building up an integrated system, each bringing their piece to the puzzle, and allowing this system to be tested in real scale. Findings from research organisations could be transferred to SMEs and industry, that would then together test them at field level. Public authorities could support manufacturing on a small (and medium?) scale basis.

2.2.3.2 Recommendations only for SMEs

Another option is to promote actions dedicated only to SMEs. The EIB report proposes a set of specific measures to address the needs of SMEs, both from the public and the private side, in the next few years. Although the document addresses 5G, recommendations focusing on “SMEs that are active in the 5G domain” could be adapted to the context of components for 6G. Among the recommendations proposed in the report, the following ones seem relevant to look into, in the context of COREnect:

- Dedicate specific budget envelopes within MFF 2021-2027 programmes to SMEs working on 5G/advanced connectivity solutions.
- Launch an indirect funding programme mobilizing venture capital and corporate investment.
- Develop a 5G-focused co-investment platform for VC funds.

Some experts recommend in COREnect’s consultation to strengthen specific support to SMEs via dedicated SME funding programmes, programmes reserved to cooperation between research institutions and SMEs, e.g., to form integrated technology 5G/6G hubs, and pre-commercial projects.

The major players in such actions are the public authorities and primarily the European Commission, and on the other hand private stakeholders, in particular corporate companies. Those recommendations could be adapted as follow in the context of COREnect to determine the critical investments that need to be done in the coming years:

- **Specific budget envelopes within Horizon Europe shall be dedicated to SMEs working on components for future connectivity systems.** This could be achieved e.g., by a joint effort between the KDT and SNS Partnerships.
- **Corporate participation in “targeted investments in venture capital (VC) funds that finance early-stage SMEs developing advanced connectivity applications” should be encouraged.** In the context of components for 6G, both microelectronics and telecommunications corporates (equipment manufacturers as well as telecommunications operators) should be involved. In addition, corporates from vertical sectors that shall primarily benefit from European-based components for 6G, e.g., automotive or manufacturing.
- The creation of a “dedicated 5G co-investment platform”, to provide SMEs with the opportunity to grow, is another recommendation from the report. A recommendation from COREnect could be to **create a dedicated co-investment platform focusing on components for 6G**, involving corporate VCs from both the microelectronics and telecommunications sector, as well as those from the vertical sectors.

On 20 April 2021, the heads of 33 European unicorn companies called for a 100-billion-euro technology sovereignty fund [CEO21]. 6G wireless networks is among the few technologies mentioned as being candidate for Important Projects of European Common Interest (IPCEI). Such an IPCEI is already happening in the microelectronics domain. COREnect is trying to include in that IPCEI activities around components for 6G. However, it is unclear how much contribution is expected from SMEs in this IPCEI (<https://www.ipcei-me.eu/what-is/>) - preliminary information indicate that Europe is counting on the large players⁴.

Another recommendation that could apply to SMEs in the COREnect domain is to **create “Pan-EU sandboxes”**, that would provide SMEs with a “frictionless way to access the EU market”. According to the unicorn CEOs, “a Pan-EU sandbox would be a one-stop shop where a company would apply for approval and would be automatically eligible to offer products and services throughout the EU market”. This is particularly critical in the 6G domain with the much-fragmented EU telecommunications market, not to mention the often-fragmented vertical sectors domains. Such regulatory sandboxes have already been put in place at Member State level, e.g., in Finland since 2015 for their 5G Tests Network Finland (5GTNF), or in France in 2019 for the creation of 5G trial platforms in the 26 GHz band, and should be broadened to encompass all EU countries.

Another issue that needs to be improved in Europe is the efficiency and effectiveness of distributing funds to start-ups. The recent example of the EIC freezing submissions for a 1B€ start-up fund shall be prevented [EIC21]. When it comes to innovation in the 5G/6G and components domains, time is of the essence. Effectiveness could be strengthened by establishing a dedicated start-up scoreboard, as proposed by a group of composed of representatives from various start-up-oriented organisations, “to track innovation performance across EU start-ups” [SCORE21]. Other recommendations include to set up a more coherent policymaking on start-ups, to incentivise public institutions to spend more on procurement from EU start-ups, and to promote entrepreneurship and provide more support to female entrepreneurs [STARTUP21]. All those recommendations apply as well to the SMEs in the domain covered by COREnect.

To overcome the IPR and patent issue, one expert responding to COREnect’s consultation suggested to offer under-used patents to SMEs for free, and ask for licencing fees only if the eventual products become successful.

Several 5G trial infrastructures are being supported by the 5G PPP and are also planned to be supported in the upcoming SNS Partnership, with a specific objective of being open to SMEs willing to test their products and solutions, considering that most SMEs cannot invest themselves in building up such a test bed. COREnect shall recommend that **components should be included in the upcoming 5G/6G trial infrastructures**.

The SMEs were hit harder than large companies by the pandemic crisis. Recovery packages put in place by many countries included supporting innovation and entrepreneurship. OECD insists that the needs of SMEs shall be considered and that it is important to include SMES and entrepreneurs in consultations on the policy response to the pandemic [OECD21]. In a similar manner, COREnect could recommend that **the needs of SMEs shall be considered and that SMEs shall be included in future policy and financing consultations**.

⁴ As stated in <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/eu-promises-significant-funds-boost-local-semiconductor-production>

2.2.3.3 General recommendations applicable to SMEs

Finally, there are general recommendations that, if followed, would have a great impact on SMEs. The first example is the strategy of Europe on its “technological sovereignty”, that needs to be clarified. Without a clear EU strategy towards a future technological sovereignty, SMEs are facing uncertainties about some of their potentially large customers, that could originate from outside the EU. Should they continue working for such customers, pending the possibility that their products might possibly be prevented to enter the EU market? MEPs are pushing the EC for a clearer strategy, highlighting that such a strategy should be clearly related to the private and public partnerships within Horizon Europe, especially when it comes to semiconductors and microprocessors [MEP21]. One recommendation is therefore to **establish a clear link between the overall EU industrial strategy leading to more technological sovereignty in the domain of components for 6G, and the activities of the SNS and KDT Partnerships.**

A recent report from a German think tank stressed that EU should focus in the near future on advanced chip design rather than on chip manufacturing [BRIEF21]. If Europe’s strategy was to follow such a recommendation, then this could open up opportunities for start-ups and SMEs.

Another important issue for SMEs working on vertical solutions and products is that the **investment should not necessarily be limited to Horizon Europe**. Maria da Graca Carvalho, a MEP well known for her active involvement in research related matters, proposed that “[innovation] should be spread across the entire EU framework of regional policy, agriculture and structural funds” [MARKET21]. This applies particularly well to the domain of 5G/6G, where much innovation shall spread to vertical sectors.

To overcome the issue of market fragmentation in Europe, particularly harmful to SMEs, the *5G Supply Market Trends* report recommends to increase R&I investment in 5G development in Europe, overcome the tendency of investing at national level, thus preventing “cohesion and scale in public initiatives”, and to create a dedicated policy including “funding and financial support for new players entering the 5G supply market”. This idea is also supported by The European Digital SME Alliance, who stresses the need to “create an SME-friendly business environment and harmonized rules that allow business to easily engage in cross-border business activities” [MANIF19].

The *5G Supply Market Trends* report also recommends to promote international standards for 5G, as this could “open up the supply market landscape to smaller hardware and solution providers or start-ups and promote the diversity of players in the 5G supply market”.

Finally, one of the challenges faced by SMEs and listed in section 2.2.2 is the high upfront chip development costs. Here, a possible path could be the support in EU of an open-source computing HW (OSCHW) ecosystem, which holds the promises of lowering entry costs for new chip designs, as discussed on June 17th in a consultation workshop⁵ organised on behalf of the European Commission by the three Industrial Associations AENEAS, ARTEMIS, and EPoSS. EU funding could:

- Facilitate OSCHW prototyping (Europractice-like), including: (1) tech access & Multi-Product Wafer costs, (2) enablement + IO/PHY IP costs, (3) access to advanced EDA tools & expertise, and (4) design implementation support & expertise.
- Nurture & support the ecosystem, including: (1) EU-support for OpenHW Group around RISC-V, (2) the development of a commercial EU IP ecosystem, (3) EU EDA tooling for research and companies, and (4) education-centric initiatives & training.

⁵ <https://ecscollaborationtool.eu/consultation-workshop.html>

3 Interim Report on Outreach, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy

3.1 Current outreach of the COREnect ecosystem

Deliverable 4.1 explained that MS Teams was selected to engage with the experts, especially those from the COREnect Expert Groups, considering that the COREnect project targets deep involvement of, and open communication with, their experts. To stimulate this, the COREnect team has created a dedicated MS Teams workspace which is broadly accessible by all experts from within and outside the consortium. Today, more than 100 persons have access to this workspace. All these experts have equal rights to consult and edit the shared material, and to use the MS Teams features to communicate, brainstorm and interact. Still, we have structured the workspace such that experts can easily connect with the community within their expertise domain. According to the three expert groups defined in the project, we have created the corresponding chat channels and SharePoint folders.

Over the last few months, this workspace was used extensively by the experts, especially the SharePoint feature. This feature enabled experts to jointly draft documents and to respond dynamically on each other's writings. Moreover, this feature acts as a repository to share and archive all kind of digital material. Some expert groups also used their chat function to discuss certain topics. Although the MS Teams workspace also allows to setup telco's and to capture the meeting minutes, it showed that the members mainly used their own telco licenses and archived the meeting minutes into dedicated documents stored onto the workspace.

Some experts encountered some difficulties to access the MS Teams workspace at first, but such problems were resolved rather quickly. Adding additional members is fairly easy, and all members can access via their professional login credentials. This strongly enhances the ease of access and stimulates the usage.

Expert recruitment & public consultation:

In relation to the recruitment of experts, AUSTRALO carried out several actions:

- An article was released on the COREnect website to locate EG1 experts in the field of Compute & Store. This article explained the role that the expert was going to play within the group, as well as the conditions and benefits to be obtained.
- Engagement of the experts was performed via social media. About 55% of the traffic comes from Twitter and 45% from LinkedIn⁶, with the expert recruitment counting for about 26% of the sessions on Twitter and 42% on LinkedIn.
- A public consultation was launched, counting for about 2.5% of the sessions on both Twitter and LinkedIn.
- An email campaign was launched within target stakeholders for the EG recruitment and public consultation.

⁶ Figures from Google Analytics.

In addition, **social media campaigns** in the COREnect social channels and on the 5GPPP LinkedIn Group were carried out, with the intention of adding experts in the Compute & Store Group, and getting answers to the public consultation.

After this first action to search for experts for EG1, 4 experts showed interest in taking part in the EG1. A total of 7 people answered the public consultation.

Apart from this EG1 expert recruitment, a **permanent recruitment campaign** was launched, emphasizing the need to search for female experts and experts from SMEs. 6 people have shown interest so far.

5G IA and AENEAS supported the recruitment of experts and the participation in the public consultation to contribute to shaping the roadmap for core components and subsystem technologies for Beyond-5G and 6G networks. In particular, information and material (e.g., COREnect's newsletter and press release) were timely and widely distributed among the 5G PPP and 'Smart Networks and Services' communities and the AENEAS and ECS communities, via several mailing lists. This was echoed on the 5G PPP and AENEAS websites, newflashes and social media. This allowed to reach thousands of people from relevant stakeholder organisations and, for the press releases, around 300 selected journalists.

COREnect 2nd Internal Workshop on 11 March 2021.

Following an earlier workshop on “what” to achieve, this one was more focused on “how” to achieve the secure supply of trustable components for Beyond 5G/6G deployment. The agenda was the following:

- Introduction and set the scene
- Partner presentations
 - Imagine possible failure modes (and potential causes, likelihood of occurrence) on securing trusted components for B5G/6G deployment
 - For each of this envisioned failure mode, what would be the consequences to
 - Each partner
 - Each industry/community
 - Europe (everyone)
 - What is partner's desired future and how to reach it?
 - Partner itself
 - Industry/community
 - Europe (everyone)
- Structured discussion
 - Derive priorities of the issues to be tackled to avoid unwanted consequences and reach the desired future based on severity and probability of detection
 - For high priority issues, list possible prevention and/or mitigation measures
 - Assess the cost and feasibility of those measures

In the end, the agenda proved too ambitious for the time available and conclusions could not be reached, however a compilation document with inputs from all partners was created, which provided a very good basis for further work, in particular within Work Package 2.

COREnect workshop and Panel: EuCNC & 6G Summit on the 08 and 10 June 2021.

- Workshop “Hardware Enabling Technologies for 6G Networks” – June 8th, 14:00 – 17:30 CEST (<https://www.eucnc.eu/workshops/workshop-2/>). Combining insights and expertise from the communication and microelectronics domains, the three expert groups addressed three key areas and shared their sector-specific views points on:

- a) Electronics for Trustworthy Communication (6G and beyond),
- b) Future Core Technologies and Integration and
- c) Energy-efficient, Green Communication Electronics.

There were between 62 and 75 participants in this workshop. This is quite a good result, considering that there were 8 sessions running in parallel, and that there was a workshop dedicated to the Hexa-X flagship project running concurrently. The participation was stable all along the workshop, demonstrating a permanent presence from the audience throughout the workshop.

- Panel “Components and Hardware on the Road to 6G” - June 10th 11:30 – 13:00 CEST (<https://www.eucnc.eu/panel-2/>).

The panel elaborated on the first COREnect’s findings and results related to the expected role of microelectronics in 6G. Ideas and recommendations on strategic measures to address these challenges, as well as the potential roles of the various stakeholders in such future 6G ecosystems (e.g., industry, SMEs, academia, associations, public authorities, etc.), were also discussed.

352 participants watched the panel. Here as well, the audience remained present for the whole duration of the panel⁷.

Besides a COREnect article on the website, an email campaign and a social media campaign were put in place in order to promote the participation in the event. Promotion was also made in the COREnect newsletter released on the 3rd of June. The website got a peak of visitors the day the newsletter was released.

⁷ Figures provided by EuCNC organisation

During the event, live social media posts were published on the COREnect social media channels.

Example of a social media post released before the event:

During the event:

COREnect session at the 5G PPP Technology Board on 21 May, 16:30 -17:15 CEST

COREnect’s session was entitled “Microelectronics and components for 6G networks” and it covered the following topics:

- General introduction of COREnect
- Strategy & vision of COREnect
- Introduction to the 3 Expert Groups and their topic areas
- Q&A Discussion

This was a great opportunity to raise awareness on COREnect’s activities and ambitions among the Technical Managers of the other 5G PPP projects. It was also an occasion to get feedback from the other projects and to inform about the possibilities to contribute and be involved in COREnect’s work (e.g. to recruit additional experts, to establish closer contacts with relevant 5G PPP projects).

More than 200 people attended the Technology Board meeting.

Closer relationship between the ECS and the SNS communities

The active participation of COREnect in the main events of the ECS and SNS communities (respectively EF ECS and EuCNC) paved the way for an increased collaboration between the two communities. In addition, COREnect has been actively participating in 5G PPP activities, e.g., Steering Board (SB) and Technical Board (TB) meetings. In particular, an introductory presentation was given in Architecture WG. Such exchange was further relayed via invitations extended by AENEAS to SNS experts to become part of the teams developing the ECS Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, which is the basis for the KDT future calls. In particular, the Chairwomen of the 2021 ECS SRIA, Elisabeth Steimetz, was interviewed for the COREnect newsletter #2, released in February 2021. This resulted in several SNS experts volunteering for contributions in the current ECS SRIA update. In the same vein, an internal workshop between COREnect consortium and SNS WP editorial team and the corresponding discussions will continue in next months.

3.1.1 Reaching out to the COREnect users

COREnect attended several meetings of the Mobility.E Lighthouse and participated in the Symposium on June 17th. In a panel discussion on “Trends and Acceleration for Electric, Connected and Automated Mobility”, the viewpoints from different perspectives have been given, more in particular OEM, connectivity, semiconductors and long-term R&D. From a communication perspective, the importance of 5/6G and the cloud connection was emphasized, whereby performance, efficiency and reliability were considered as key requirements.

In the framework of the internal report “IR2.1 Revised vision and requirement report” in WP2, contacts have been established with the automotive industry.

In the second year of the project, other strategic verticals sectors to be selected by COREnect should be approached. The MoUs that the 5G IA signed with a number of prominent European verticals associations should be used to support those interactions.

3.1.2 Dissemination and promotion activities

Key dissemination and promotion activities have been successfully carried out as planned in the first six months of 2021:

- A press release was issued in January 2021.
- COREnect issued its 2nd and 3rd newsletter in February and June 2021.
- Some major updates have been done to the COREnect website.
- COREnect’s social media strategy has been put in place.
- AENEAS disseminates the COREnect activities to the ECS community and 5G IA to the SNS community via their newsletters / newsflashes, social media, and mailing lists, and to their press contacts.
- COREnect participates in the New 5G Core Technologies Innovation Projects webinar
- The 2nd COREnect workshop was held within the EUCNC & 6G Summit on 08-10 June 2021.

The following subsections describe in detail the activities performed with respect to dissemination and promotion in COREnect.

3.1.2.1 COREnect web site

The initial website was set up in September 2020 and has been updated in the period of time in which the project is framed. So far, it has served as a general presentation of the purpose of the COREnect project, showing information about the different working packages, expert groups, news, publications, consortium, etc.

A webpage for publications has been added to publish the COREnect deliverables, the newsletters and press releases.

The Consortium and the EG pages have been updated.

A video has been added to the website and different articles have been published on the News webpage: COREnect General Assembly (28.01.2021), COREnect participates in the New 5G Core Technologies Innovation Projects webinar (18.02.2121), COREnect is opening a permanent call for new experts (06.04.2021), COREnect on the road to EuCNC & 6G Summit (15.04.2021), COREnect in the European 5G Annual Journal 2021 (27.05.2021), The 6G White Paper, an interview with Carlos Jesús Bernardos Cano (03.06.2021).

(screenshot of the newspage)

(Screenshot of the Publications' page)

3.1.2.2 COREnect social media

The LinkedIn and Twitter social channels are still being used to build a community around the challenges COREnect faces, and to expand the communications in relation with the events in which the consortium participates. The social channels are managed (internally) thanks to a posting calendar helping to schedule the content, daily and weekly.

The marketing strategy is adapted to each of the channels. Twitter is used towards a broader audience, while LinkedIn focuses on longer posts that should be more relevant for technical experts.

Relevant profiles are monitored, and information that is interesting to COREnect is published.

On LinkedIn, COREnect is trying to participate in third-party conversations about related challenges. There is a community strategy for recommending posts of people who have shared COREnect’s posts. In both social networks, COREnect promotes articles and events in which some of the partners participate, starting with its own events.

As a conclusion for the social media channels: COREnect has a more professional audience on LinkedIn, But the project has a wide audience on TW that likes to be aware of what COREnect does. As COREnect gets more traffic from Twitter than from LinkedIn.

Social Network	Sessions	% Sessions
1. Twitter	19	76.00%
2. LinkedIn	5	20.00%

Twitter: 342 followers

Average profile visits in the last 3 months: 1000 visits

LinkedIn: 174 followers

Average profile visits in the last 3 months: 22 visitors.

3.1.2.3 COREnect newsletters

The 2nd and 3rd COREnect newsletters were issued on February 1st, and 3rd June, 2021. They were broadly disseminated to the ECS and SNS communities, using the 5G IA and the AENEAS dissemination means.

COREnect published 2 articles with the newsletters on the News page of the website, along with a specific section on the Publications webpage with the newsletters. Both newsletters included an editorial from Gerhard Fettweis, COREnect project coordinator.

The 2nd Newsletter included: A strategy and vision for building European technological sovereignty in 5G and beyond, The Initial COREnect Ecosystems, The new ECS SRIA: An Interview with Elisabeth Steimetz, COREnect initial Roadmap ideas, Call for Experts in Computing and Storage and 2nd Press Release.

The 3rd Newsletter included: EuCNC information, COREnect stakeholder pictures, 6G White Paper: An interview with Carlos Jesús Bernardos Cano, “Pre-release” of D3.3 Initial COREnect industry roadmap, COREnect in the European 5GAnnual Journal 202 and COREnect permanent call for new experts.

03.06.2021
Newsletter
COREnect

EDITORIAL

We are excited about the outcome of the first step towards a significant delivery of the project. We shall give the EC and our society an insight into the main areas of technology that are essential for delivering 5G and 6G solutions of the future. COREnect and its amazing team of nearly 100 experts have identified some technology areas within three Expert Groups.

You can read below the Editorial by Gerhard P. Fettweis, Vodafone Chair Professor, COREnect Project Coordinator, TU Dresden.

EDITORIAL

EUCNC | 6G Summit
Porto, Portugal, 8-11 June 2021
On the Road to 6G

"Hardware Enabling Technologies for 6G Networks" workshop
Tuesday, 8 June 2021, 14:00-15:30/16:00-17:30 CEST

AGENDA

EUCNC | 6G Summit
Virtual Conference, Porto, Portugal, 8-11 June 2021

"Components and Hardware on the Road to 6G" panel
Thursday, 10 June, 11:30-13:00 CEST.

AGENDA

3.1.2.4 COREnect press releases

COREnect’s 2nd press release was issued in January 2021. All project partners contributed to its preparation and agreed on its content.

The press release was widely distributed on the COREnect website, COREnect social media channels, and was relayed by 5G IA and AENEAS, as well as all other COREnect partners.

4 Interim Achievements, Conclusions and Next Steps

This section provides a summary of the achievements in WP4 from the last six months of the project, in relation with the objectives in the DoA.

4.1 Interim achievements vs. COREnect objectives

Sub-objectives	Measure of Achievement	Already achieved	
1.a	<i>COREnect will bring together the stakeholders that should be involved in such a community, starting with the organisations involved in this project, in the ICT-42 Innovation Actions, and in the existing communities where part of the stakeholders shall be involved, primarily the SNS and KDT communities.</i>	<i>Initiate and proceed with the creation of a dedicated “European Core Technologies for future connectivity systems” community, i.e. the COREnect community.</i>	COREnect provisioning ecosystem picture has been revised (cf. section 2.1.1). It is an important reference for the project and relevant stakeholders are engaged.
2.a	<i>Organisation of a COREnect workshop by 5G IA and AENEAS for knowledge sharing on this topic.</i>	<i>Obtain reciprocal knowledge of current Strategic Research Agendas and processes for elaboration.</i>	The 2nd COREnect internal Workshop on 11 March 2021 as well as the Panel and Workshop organised at the joint EuCNC & 6G Summit have been successful events (cf. section 3.1).
2.b	<i>Availability of a mapping of relevant contributing experts of both communities, providing inputs for recruiting and engaging external technical experts for roadmapping activities.</i>	<i>Identification of the contributors of the two Strategic Research Agendas pertinent to the definition of a roadmap of core technologies for future connectivity systems.</i>	Contributors to the sections that are most relevant to COREnect in the ECS SRIA and the NetworldEurope SRIA were identified in D4.1. Further interactions to involve each community in the upcoming SRIA effort of the other community has been initiated.
3.b	<i>COREnect will engage with the industrial, academic and SME communities to make them aware of the new community being built up and of the opportunities that it brings in economic and societal terms. To do so, it will disseminate effective material to the most relevant external stakeholders and invite those stakeholders in workshops and events to make them aware of what this community will produce in the future.</i>	<i>Promote the preliminary results obtained by the COREnect community to engage and mobilise potential future “champions” as well as potential future users and investors.</i>	The 2nd and 3rd COREnect newsletters, the second press release “<i>Providing a roadmap for core components and sub-system technologies for Beyond-5G and 6G networks</i>”, COREnect events, activity on social media, the public consultation, and the release of the first project deliverables, allowed to effectively inform and engage the ECS and SNS communities.

4.2 Interim achievements in relation to the meetings of the COREnect Expert Groups

A total of 104 experts are registered in the EGs, representing 54 different organisations. 46% of the experts come from industry, and 54% from research institutes, universities and one European agency. Details have been laid out in section 3.1.1.2. The following table describes the initial achievements in relation with the expected impact of the project when it comes to roadmapping:

Expected impact - Indicators	Initial results achieved
Number of industry domains involved in the roadmapping activities	At this initial stage, only ECS and SNS stakeholders have been involved in the EGs, as they constitute the basis of the COREnect community.
Number of industry domains to which COREnect disseminates the roadmap	n/a (the roadmap is not available yet).
Number of large enterprises and SMEs involved in the roadmapping activities	29 large companies and SMEs have been involved in the EGs.
Number of feedbacks received from large enterprises and SMEs across Europe	n/a (the roadmap is not available yet).
Number of industry associations to which COREnect disseminates the roadmap	n/a (the roadmap is not available yet).

4.3 Interim dissemination achievements

- 2nd Press release: 36 downloads⁸
- "Pre-release" of D3.3 Initial COREnect industry roadmap: 119 downloads
- COREnect Stakeholder Pictures 01.06.2021: 69 downloads
- COREnect Newsletter3 EuCNC Panel: 88 downloads
- COREnect Newsletter3 EuCNC Workshop: 95 downloads
- COREnect Newsletter3 6G White paper Interview: 33 downloads
- COREnect Newsletter#3 Editorial: 81 downloads
- Average users of the website in a month: 250 users.
- Average visits in a month: 303
- COREnect D1.1 Project Management Plan and Tools: 29 downloads.
- COREnect Deliverable 2.1 Initial vision and requirement report: 263 downloads.
- COREnect Deliverable 3.1 Report on the activities of expert groups: 151 Downloads.
- COREnect Deliverable 4.1 Initial report on community building and outreach strategy: 110 Downloads.

⁸ The Zenodo platform had a problem with the COREnect account in April 2021, and the count of document downloads was lost. This number is therefore below the actual number of downloads.

4.4 Conclusions and next steps

WP4 significantly contributed to the progress made on the three main project objectives, i.e., bringing together the relevant stakeholders that form the COREnect community; establishing a two-way communication with the SNS and KDT communities; and effectively disseminating results to the external stakeholders to encourage them in the future to be part of the community or use its results.

In the second year of the project, if the situation related to the Covid-19 pandemic continues to improve, we envisage the organisation of and participation in physical meetings and events.

4.4.1 Community building

Although progress has been made on the three aspects of stakeholder identification, stakeholder engagement, and SMEs in the COREnect ecosystem, more needs to be done during the 2nd year of the COREnect project.

4.4.1.1 Stakeholder identification

The initial stakeholder pictures have been revised and presents today a better idea of the stakeholders that are part of the COREnect community and who are the potential users of the COREnect-related products and solutions in the future. Those pictures, along with the accompanying glossary, need to be worked further to fine tune the engagement activities that will be performed during Year 2 of the project. In particular:

- The stakeholders involved in the development and deployment of components for 6G, at the crossroad of ECS and SNS, should be better identified;
- The stakeholders involved in using the components in their 6G-related products shall be better identified, both as part of the COREnect community (i.e., the ones developing 6G-related products and solutions), and in the use case community (i.e., the ones who need to use 6G-related products to develop innovative solutions dedicated to vertical sectors);
- We need to better understand the role that could be played by the stakeholders from the complementary industry and research on the one hand, and technology users / intermediaries, in the COREnect ecosystems.

Besides, the following comments need to be considered for the next stage:

- The ECS “categorization” might need to be further revised. For example, the term “service provider” may mean “IC design houses” or “IC design service providers”, that is different. The difference between “material suppliers” and “material providers” need to be clarified, as well as the position of the foundries. The classification of the ECS SRIA might be a good basis to follow.
- The list of initiatives and projects can never be complete, and may be perceived as excluding others. This should be better explained.

4.4.1.2 SMEs in the COREnect ecosystems

An initial analysis has been performed to better understand the potential role of SMEs and to prepare recommendations that will address this important part of the 6G ecosystem in WP2 and WP3. The next steps shall focus on the following:

- Consider the final version of the “5G Ecosystem White Paper” that shall be released in the summer of 2021 by 5G IA, apply this model to COREnect, and see whether this could be expanded towards 6G as far as the COREnect ecosystems are concerned⁹;
- Progress further on the potential recommendations for investment and roadmap when considering the European SME ecosystem, as a contribution to WP2 and WP3;
- Consider the first work programmes of SNS and KDT and the role of SMEs in those programmes.

4.4.1.3 Stakeholder engagement

Stakeholders have been engaged during Year 1 of the projects through multiple means. D4.1 had listed a number of organisations potentially relevant for the COREnect community. There is no doubt that COREnect has already engaged many relevant stakeholders, especially via its Expert Groups, but also via the events and social channels. Year 2 shall continue on this trend, and further refine the targeted stakeholders, based on the progress made when it comes to the stakeholder identification. The organisations involved in the first SNS and KDT calls shall be looked upon, especially if there are call topics that relate to components for 5G and 6G. Progress of the microelectronics IPCEI shall also be monitored, to check the stakeholders involved.

Another important activity that shall be monitored by COREnect to engage with the relevant stakeholders is the effort dedicated to the next versions of the ECS and NetworldEurope SRIAs.

The 5G IA, in the framework of the preparation of the “Smart Networks and Services” partnership under Horizon Europe, is widening its membership to include verticals and key sectors/stakeholders. Many contacts are ongoing also with EU institutions and Member States. 5G IA works to link and align COREnect’s activities to the SNS programme in order to create positive synergies.

The possibility to approach strategic verticals sectors (as it was already done with the automotive sector for the preparation of IR2.1) will be carefully considered.

4.4.2 Communication and dissemination

From the point of view of communication, much emphasis is being placed on disseminating COREnect's participation in events and in publications.

Interactions with other European projects related to 5G and components could be considered for Year2 of the project, e.g., for joint actions and mutual promotion, as well as promoting the reports and results obtained. This might be done in a bilateral basis, as the 5G PPP COMMS Group has not been very active and will likely become even less active with the completion of the Full5G CSA at the end of the summer of 2021.

The next deliverables will continue to be published both in Zenodo (open access) and on the COREnect website.

The social media actions will continue to have the objective of making the project known, and moreover the results that are being obtained.

⁹ The White Paper is also relevant for the stakeholder identification aspect, but it is much oriented towards SMEs, hence its interest for the role and positioning of SMEs.

Following earlier interactions with the ECS communities, most notably during EF ECS in November 2020, a lot of interactions with SNS community have been carried out in Spring 2021. Note that these interactions involved prominent members of the ECS community, e.g. during the EuCNC panel. COREnect will capture the momentum established via a series of activities outlined in D4.2 and continue the dialogue and interactions with the ECS and the SNS communities in the second year of its operation.

COREnect will make sure that the interactions of ECS and SNS community move steadily forward and will seek the establishment of official communication channels between the two communities.

As foreseen in the DoA, a “workshop dedicated to policy makers will be organised in June or September 2022 in Brussels, e.g., at the European Parliament (EP) or at EC premises”.

A presentation to at least one standardisation body (e.g., ETSI) is also foreseen in 2022.

Participation in EF ECS and EuCNC is planned in 2021-2022.

Following the positive experience in May 2021, COREnect could be invited again to have a session during a 5G PPP Technology Board meeting in 2022. This would contribute to further raise awareness among the 5G PPP and SNS communities and facilitate positive exchanges and synergies.

References

- [Joint21] “Joint declaration on processors and semiconductor technologies”, 07/12/2020. <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/joint-declaration-processors-and-semiconductor-technologies>
- [AENEAS-SME] “SME Members Directory”, AENEAS, <https://aeneas-office.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/AENEAS-SME-Members-Directory-2910.pdf>
- [EIB21] “Accelerating the 5G transition in Europe. How to boost investments in transformative 5G solutions”, European Investment Bank, 2021. <https://www.eib.org/en/publications/accelerating-the-5g-transition-in-europe>
- [AIT21-1] “5G Supply Market Trends – Workshop Preparatory Report”, Austrian Institute of Technology, 08/12/2020. http://widgixeu-library.s3.amazonaws.com/library/90008426/5GWorkshop_Preparatory_Report.pdf
- [AIT21-2] “5G Supply Market Trends. Background Paper. Second Stakeholder Workshop on May 19th, 2021”, Austrian Institute of Technology, 12 May 2021, <https://zenodo.org/record/4752718#.YKYUp6E6-70>
- [SRC21] “Decadal Plan for Semiconductors. Full Report”, Semiconductor Research Corporation, January 2021. <https://www.src.org/about/decadal-plan/>
- [GABRIEL20] “Gabriel outlines principles for a single European market for innovation”, 8 December 2020. <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/gabriel-outlines-principles-single-european-market-innovation>
- [FR21] “French programme launches to transform EU’s tech underachiever status”, 4 March 2021. <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/french-programme-launches-transform-eus-tech-underachiever-status>
- [CEO21] “Leading CEOs call for €100B technology sovereignty fund”, 20 April 2021. <https://sciencebusiness.net/technology-strategy-board/news/leading-ceos-call-eu100b-technology-sovereignty-fund>
- [SCORE21] “Call for start-up scoreboard to track Europe’s innovation progress”, 11 May 2021, <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/call-start-scoreboard-track-europes-innovation-progress>
- [STARTUP21] “Action Plan to Make Europe the new Global Powerhouse for Startups. Challenging EU institutions and Member States. Where do we want to see Europe in the area of startups in five years?”, 10 May 2021, <https://europeanstartupnetwork.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Action-Plan-to-Make-Europe-the-new-Global-Powerhouse-for-Startups.pdf>
- [OECD21] “One year of SME and entrepreneurship policy responses to COVID-19. Lessons learned to ‘build back bet-ter’”, OECD, 8 April 2021, <https://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/one-year-of-sme-and-entrepreneurship-policy-responses-to-covid-19-lessons-learned-to-build-back-better-9a230220/>

- [MEP21] “MEPs grill Breton over role of research partnerships in industrial strategy”, 11 May 2021, <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/meps-grill-breton-over-role-research-partnerships-industrial-strategy>
- [BRIEF21] “The lack of semiconductor manufacturing in Europe. Why the 2nm fab is a bad investment”, Policy Brief, March 2021, Stiftung Neue Verantwortung, Think Tank at the Intersection of Technology and Society, <https://www.stiftung-nv.de/de/publikation/lack-semiconductor-manufacturing-europe>
- [MARKET21] “Gabriel outlines principles for a single European market for innovation”, 8 December 2020. <https://sciencebusiness.net/news/gabriel-outlines-principles-single-european-market-innovation>
- [MANIF19] “Manifesto for Europe’s Digital Future. A Way Forward for the EU Mandate 2019-2024”, European Digital SME Alliance, https://www.digitalsme.eu/digital/uploads/DIGITAL-SME-Manifesto_final.pdf

Annex A: COREnect Stakeholder Glossary

Term	Definition	References
THE COREnect COMMUNITY		
5G/6G Industry and Research		
5G/6G Complementary Industry		
IT providers	IT providers provide equipment, software, and IT Services.	European IT observatory. (2018). <i>ICT Market report 2018/19</i> . Berlin: European IT observatory.
OT Providers	Providers of Operational technology (OT), which is hardware and software that detects or causes a change, through the direct monitoring and/or control of industrial equipment, assets, processes and events. The term has become established to demonstrate the technological and functional differences between traditional IT systems and Industrial Control Systems environment, the so-called "IT in the non-carpeted areas".	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Operational_technology
OTT providers	An over-the-top (OTT) media service is a streaming media service offered directly to viewers via the Internet. OTT bypasses cable, broadcast, and satellite television platforms, the companies that traditionally act as a controller or distributor of such content.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Over-the-top_media_service
System integrators	Systems integration can be defined as a process that includes the planning, design, implementation, and project management of a technical solution that addresses an organization's specific technical or business needs. When SI deals involve contracting for custom application development (CAD) related to the systems integration, then those activities are included in the definition of SI. SI projects typically involve different platforms and technologies. The solution may include hardware, software, and services and is consumed on premise, on demand, or in a cloud-based environment. An SI project is formalized by a contract that is constructed around solution specifications and often demands certain levels of performance against technical or business goals. The end result of an SI project is the delivery of a system that meets a stated objective and fulfills solution specifications.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Systems_integrator
Service enablers	Cf. <i>System integrators</i> *	<i>Ibid.</i>
Digital service providers	In the context of digital in the Information Society, 'service' "is to say, any service normally provided for remuneration, at a distance, by electronic means and at the individual request of a recipient of services". The provider of such services are digital service providers.	Directive (EU) 2015/1535, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32015L1535
Connectivity providers		
Connectivity providers	Connectivity providers perform day-to-day operational activities to provide network connection via wired/wireless networks.	https://www.ispcp.info/

(Mobile) network operators	(Mobile) network providers are companies that provide customers with access to a (mobile) telecommunications network or to the Internet.	http://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/network-provider
Small cells operators	Small cell is a growing technology that enables Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) to deploy sites in strategic locations offering smaller coverage with higher capacities, using licensed and unlicensed wireless spectrum.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Small_cell
Hotspot providers	Hotspot providers arrange the Internet access, typically using Wi-Fi technology, via a wireless local area network (WLAN) using a router connected to an internet service provider. Coffee shops, airports and hotels are typical examples of the hotspot providers.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hotspot_(Wi-Fi)
Cloud/edge providers	Edge computing primarily refers to bringing processing and storage capabilities closer to where it is needed.	https://stlpartners.com/edge-computing/edge-computing-companies-2020/
Service providers	Service providers in telecommunications sector are companies that provide their subscribers with access to the Internet and/or other value-added services, e.g. cloud computing, storage and e-learning.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Service_provider
OTT providers	An over-the-top (OTT) media service is a streaming media service offered directly to viewers via the Internet. OTT bypasses cable, broadcast, and satellite television platforms, the companies that traditionally act as a controller or distributor of such content.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Over-the-top_media_service
Apps & solution providers	An application/solution service provider is a business providing computer-based solutions/services to customers over a network, such as access to a software solution/application (e.g. customer relationship management) using a standard protocol (e.g. HTTP).	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Application_service_provider
Campus networks	A campus network, campus area network, corporate area network or CAN is a computer network made up of an interconnection of local area networks (LANs) within a limited geographical area.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Campus_network
Technology providers and developers		
Technology providers and developers	A technology provider is a provider that develops and provides technology solution(s) which can be used by the 5G PPP projects, <i>SMEs*</i> , <i>start-ups*</i> , etc.	https://www.lawinsider.com/dictionary/technology-provider
Device & SW	A device is an object or machine - a piece of mechanical or electronic equipment - that has been invented to fulfil a particular purpose. A device typically includes a HardWare (HW) and SoftWare (SW) parts to make it independently functioning.	http://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/device
Chipset and component makers	A chipset/component maker buys raw materials from its suppliers, assembles these into chipsets/components and gives the results to other manufacturers	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chipset
Equipment manufacturers	A manufacturer is a company that produces goods in large numbers. Telecommunications equipment is a hardware which is used for the purposes of telecommunications. Since the 1990s the boundary between telecoms equipment and IT hardware has become blurred as a result of the growth of the internet and its	https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/manufacturer ; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Telecom-

	<p>increasing role in the transfer of telecoms data. An original equipment manufacturer (OEM) is a company that produces parts and equipment that may be marketed by another manufacturer.</p>	<p>munications equipment; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Original_equipment_manufacturer</p>
Developers	<p>A developer is an individual that builds and create software and applications. He or she writes, debugs and executes the source code of a software application. A developer is also known as a software developer, computer programmer, programmer, software coder or software engineer.</p>	<p>https://www.techopedia.com/definition/17095/developer</p>
Application service providers	<p>An application service provider (ASP) is a company that offers individuals or enterprises access over the Internet to applications and related services that would otherwise be in their own personal or enterprise computers.</p>	<p>http://searchsoa.techtarget.com/definition/application-service-provider</p>
<p>ECS Industry & Research</p>		
<p>Equipment and material suppliers</p>		
Semiconductors	<p>A semiconductor material has an electrical conductivity value falling between that of a conductor, such as metallic copper, and an insulator, such as glass. Its resistivity falls as its temperature rises; metals behave in the opposite way.</p>	<p>https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Semiconductor</p>
Software design	<p>Software design is the process by which an agent creates a specification of a software artifact intended to accomplish goals, using a set of primitive components and subject to constraints. Software design may refer to either "all the activity involved in conceptualizing, framing, implementing, commissioning, and ultimately modifying complex systems" or "the activity following requirements specification and before programming, a stylized software engineering process."</p>	<p>https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Software_design</p>
Semiconductor manufacturing equipment technologies	<p>Semiconductor manufacturing equipment includes systems such as oxidation systems, epitaxial reactors, diffusion systems, ion implantation equipment, physical vapor deposition systems, chemical vapor deposition systems, photolithography equipment, and etching equipment.</p>	<p>https://www.globenews-wire.com/news-release/2020/12/22/2149501/0/en/Global-131-Billion-Semiconductor-Manufacturing-Equipment-Back-end-Front-end-Markets-2020-2027.html</p>
Electronic packaging	<p>Electronic packaging is the design and production of enclosures for electronic devices ranging from individual semiconductor devices up to complete systems such as a mainframe computer.</p>	<p>https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electronic_packaging</p>
Device suppliers	<p>Suppliers of pieces of mechanical or electronic equipment designed for a particular job.</p>	<p>https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/device?q=device</p>
<p>Chip and other electronic device providers</p>		

Logic semiconductor chips	Logic semiconductors generally process the digital data for the purpose of controlling the operation of the electronic systems. On the basis of these semiconductors, any electronic devices can be operated, without them the devices cannot function for which they are designed for.	https://www.data-bridgemarket-research.com/reports/global-logic-semiconductor-market
Memory semiconductor chips	Semiconductor memory is a digital electronic semiconductor device used for digital data storage, such as computer memory. ... This contrasts with data storage media such as hard disks and CDs which read and write data consecutively and therefore the data can only be accessed in the same sequence it was written.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Semiconductor_memory
Semiconductor analog	An analog semiconductor is an electronic component that supports many functions. It may either generate a signal or transform signal characteristics, such as amplitude, phase, and frequency. Analog semiconductors are categorized as low-power or high-power audio or radio frequency applications.	https://www.in-fobloom.com/what-is-an-analog-semiconductor.htm
Components and SoC	An integrated circuit that incorporates multiple building blocks of an electronic system, including processors, memory units, accelerators, and input/output ports, and which covers the complete functionality of an electronic system.	Glossary of 2021 ECS SRIA https://aeneas-office.org/strategy/documents/
modules	Ensemble of properly integrated components so that their reunion embodies a definite functionality required for the proper working of a system (e.g. sensing and actuation module, control module, communication module, energy provision module). A module is self-contained in hardware and software, making it interchangeable between systems, and allowing higher abstraction level in systems design.	Glossary of 2021 ECS SRIA https://aeneas-office.org/strategy/documents/
Systems	A system is a set of electronic-based constituents (subsystems, modules and components, realised in hardware, software, or both) that are integrated in a way to together allow the system to perform a desired (set of) function(s).	Glossary of 2021 ECS SRIA https://aeneas-office.org/strategy/documents/
System integrators	Systems integration can be defined as a process that includes the planning, design, implementation, and project management of a technical solution that addresses an organization's specific technical or business needs. When SI deals involve contracting for custom application development (CAD) related to the systems integration, then those activities are included in the definition of SI. SI projects typically involve different platforms and technologies. The solution may include hardware, software, and services and is consumed on premise, on demand, or in a cloud-based environment. An SI project is formalized by a contract that is constructed around solution specifications and often demands certain levels of performance against technical or business goals. The end result of an SI project is the delivery of a system that meets a stated objective and fulfills solution specifications.	<i>Ibid.</i>
Electronic Design Automation	Electronic design automation (EDA), also referred to as electronic computer-aided design (ECAD), is a category of software tools for designing electronic systems such as integrated circuits and printed circuit boards. The tools work together in a design flow that chip designers use to design and analyze entire sem-	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electronic_design_automation

	iconductor chips. Since a modern semiconductor chip can have billions of components, EDA tools are essential for their design; this article in particular describes EDA specifically with respect to integrated circuits (ICs).	
Material providers		
Material: raw wafer	The raw material is polysilicon, which is refined from quartz sand by removing 99.99999999% of other elements present. The manufacturing process starts with crystal-growing, which involves growing a cylindrical single crystal out of a seed crystal of melted polysilicon. Silicon (Si) is the most commonly used material in the production of semiconductor devices because of its low raw material cost and simple manufacturing process. ... The silicon wafer used in semiconductor device fabrication has a diameter of 300 mm or 12 in.	https://www.ok-metic.com/about-us/tale-of-a-silicon-wafer
Material: commodity chemicals	Chemistry of solvents : the main chemicals used during this stage are trichloroethylene, acetone, isopropanol and also other alcohols such as denatured ethanol. The typical applications are the cleaning, the degreasing of the semiconductors and the shrinkage of residual resins (acetone).	https://www.prenvor.com/en/chemical-risks-in-semiconductors-industry/
Material: Specialty chemicals	Speciality chemicals (also called specialties or effect chemicals) are particular chemical products which provide a wide variety of effects on which many other industry sectors rely. Some of the categories of speciality chemicals are adhesives, agrichemicals, cleaning materials, colors, cosmetic additives, construction chemicals, elastomers, flavors, food additives, fragrances, industrial gases, lubricants, paints, polymers, surfactants, and textile auxiliaries. Other industrial sectors such as automotive, aerospace, food, cosmetics, agriculture, manufacturing, and textiles are highly dependent on such products.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Speciality_chemicals
Material: bulk gas	Bulk gases are the simplest molecules used in electronics manufacturing. And like water, they are piped throughout the fab to be available in almost utility-like supply.	https://siliconsemiconductor.net/article/106824/Invisible-Materials-On-site-Bulk-Gas-Supply-To-Semiconductor-And-Display-Fabs/feature
Researchers looking at		
Chip design	Integrated circuits (IC), often called chips, combine multiple discrete electronic devices onto a single substrate utilizing the capabilities of semiconductor materials. The development of the digital portions of an IC can be divided into a number of stages including: functional design and verification, physical design and verification, packaging, manufacturing test. The design of analog components, or blocks for inclusion into an IC, have a flatter flow because the functional and physical aspects cannot be separated in the same way that is possible within the digital realm.	https://semiengineering.com/knowledge_centers/eda-design/definitions/chip-design-and-verification/
Precompetitive research on semiconductors	Pre-competitive basic research is essential to the semiconductor industry and the first step in the semiconductor production process.	https://www.semiconductors.org/semiconductors-101/what-is-a-semiconductor/
COREnect related Initiatives & Projects		

Initiatives in complementary domains		
AI		
AIDA	With the goal of setting out a long-term EU roadmap on Artificial Intelligence (AI), AIDA will study the impact and challenges of rolling out AI, identify common EU-wide objectives, and propose recommendations on the best ways forward.	https://www.europarl.europa.eu/committees/en/aida/about
BDVA/DAIRO	The Big Data Value Association (BDVA) is a fully self-financed non-for-profit organisation under Belgian law. Currently there are 24 founding members from large and SME industry and research. The BDVA shall present an industry-led contractual counterpart to the European Commission for the implementation of the Big Data Value PPP cPPP. A basic principle is openness, transparency and inclusiveness. In 2020 and taking into account the end of the 2014-2020 MultiAnnual Financial Framework and the advent of the post 2020 European Commission's programmes (i.e. Horizon Europe and Digital Europe), BDVA members decided to strengthen the Association by giving it a new mandate, a new name and by expanding its scope and breadth of activities. In 2021, BDVA thus becomes DAIRO.	http://www.bdva.eu/ https://www.bdva.eu/DAIRO
ELLIS	The European Laboratory for Learning and Intelligent Systems is a pan-European nonprofit organization for the promotion of artificial intelligence with a focus on machine learning. The organization's goal is to establish top AI research institutes, strengthen basic research and create a European PhD programme for AI.	https://ellis.eu/
ETSI (ISG SAI)	The ETSI Industry Specification Group on Securing Artificial Intelligence (ISG SAI) focuses on three key areas: using AI to enhance security, mitigating against attacks that leverage AI, and securing AI itself from attack. The ETSI ISG SAI works alongside a landscape of huge growth in AI, creating standards to preserve and improve the security of Artificial Intelligence.	https://www.etsi.org/committee/1640-sai
EurAI	The European Association for Artificial Intelligence EurAI (formerly ECCAI) was established in July 1982 as a representative body for the European Artificial Intelligence community. Its aim is to promote the study, research and application of Artificial Intelligence in Europe.	https://eurai.org/
CLAIRE	An international non-profit association. The CLAIRE movement works closely with the HLG-AI, providing them with the input of the European AI communities through various mechanisms.	https://claire-ai.org/about/
Cloud		
NESSI ETP	NESSI is the European Technology Platform (ETP) dedicated to Software, Services and Data. NESSI provides input to EU Institutions on research actions and technology matters of particular importance to the software domain, and the overall aim is to enable the software and services sector help vitalize the great potential of the European economy and society. NESSI gathers Partners and Members from all over Europe, from industry, research centres and academia, and engages in close dialogue with the European Commission and other stakeholders on topics including Smart Networks and Services, Software and AI, and Key Digital Technologies.	http://www.nessi-europe.com
CISPE.Cloud	European cloud provider association.	https://cispe.cloud/
HPC		

ETSI MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) offers application developers and content providers cloud-computing capabilities and an IT service environment at the edge of the network. This environment is characterized by ultra-low latency and high bandwidth as well as real-time access to radio network information that can be leveraged by applications.	https://www.etsi.org/technologies/multi-access-edge-computing
ETP4HPC	The European Technology Platform for High Performance Computing.	https://www.etp4hpc.eu/
HIPEAC	Is a European network of almost 2,000 world-class computing systems researchers, industry representatives and students. HiPEAC provides a platform for cross-disciplinary research collaboration, promotes the transformation of research results into products and services, and is an incubator for the next generation of world-class computer scientists.	https://www.hipeac.net/
IoT		
AIOTI	The Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation (AIOTI) was initiated by the European Commission in order to develop and support the dialogue and interaction among the Internet of Things (IoT) various players in Europe. The overall goal of the AIOTI is the creation of a dynamic European IoT ecosystem to unleash the potentials of the IoT. This ecosystem is going to build on the work of the IoT Research Cluster (IERC) and spill over innovation across industries and business sectors of IoT transforming ideas into solutions and business models. The Alliance will also assist the European Commission in the preparation of future IoT research as well as innovation and standardisation policies.	http://www.aioti.eu
IIoT		
5G-ACIA	5G-ACIA is the central global forum for shaping 5G in the industrial domain. On one platform, various industries from all over the world jointly create a new ICT and OT ecosystem and set the frameworks for a highly attractive emerging market.	https://5g-acia.org/
Photonics		
Photonics Europe	<i>Photonics Europe</i> is the premier European optics and photonics conference connecting researchers with industry.	https://spie.org/conferences-and-exhibitions/photonics-europe?SSO=1
Photonics 21	The <i>European</i> Technology Platform Photonics21 represents the <i>photonics</i> community of industry and research organisations.	https://www.photonics21.org/
Big Data		
BDVA/DAIRO	The Big Data Value Association (BDVA) is a fully self-financed non-for-profit organisation under Belgian law. Currently there are 24 founding members from large and SME industry and research. The BDVA shall present an industry-led contractual counterpart to the European Commission for the implementation of the Big Data Value PPP cPPP. A basic principle is openness, transparency and inclusiveness. in 2020 and taking into account the end of the 2014-2020 MultiAnnual Financial Framework and the advent of the post 2020 European Commission's programmes (i.e. Horizon Europe and Digital Europe), BDVA members decided to strengthen the Association by giving it a new mandate, a new name and	http://www.bdva.eu/ https://www.bdva.eu/DAIRO

	by expanding its scope and breadth of activities. In 2021, BDVA thus becomes DAIRO.	
ADRA	The AI, Data and Robotics Partnership is one of the candidates for European Partnerships in digital, industry and space in Horizon Europe. To deliver the greatest benefit to Europe from AI, Data and Robotics, this Partnership will drive innovation, acceptance and uptake of these technologies.	https://ai-data-robotics-partnership.eu/
GAIA-X	is a project for the development of an efficient and competitive, secure and trustworthy federation of data infrastructure and service providers for Europe, which is supported by representatives of business, science and administration from Germany and France, together with other European partners.	https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/GAIAX/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html
IDSA	International Data Space Association: Digital transformation is a key factor for the success of companies worldwide. IDSA ensure that the special economic interests of business are specifically integrated into the research work of International Data Space. Companies can access the results of the research project on International Data Spaces on the website so they can implement these results in their own way.	https://www.internationaldataspaces.org/
Robotics		
euRobotics	euRobotics aisbl (Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif) is a Brussels based international non-profit association for all stakeholders in European robotics. It was founded in September 2012 with the aim to strengthen Europe's competitiveness and to ensure industrial leadership of manufacturers, providers and end-users of robotics technology-based systems and services.	https://www.eu-robotics.net/
ADRA	The AI, Data and Robotics Partnership is one of the candidates for European Partnerships in digital, industry and space in Horizon Europe. To deliver the greatest benefit to Europe from AI, Data and Robotics, this Partnership will drive innovation, acceptance and uptake of these technologies.	https://ai-data-robotics-partnership.eu/
Software / Embedded software		
NESSI	The Networked European Software and Services Initiative (NESSI) is the European Technology Platform (ETP) dedicated to Software, Services and Data. NESSI provides input to the EU Institutions on research actions and technology matters of particular importance to the software domain, and the overall aim is to enable the software and services sector help vitalize the great potential of the European economy and society. NESSI gathers partners and members from all over Europe, both from industry and academia, and engages in close dialogue with the European Commission and other stakeholders on several topics of specific relevance to NESSI - such as Big Data Value, Cloud Computing and Software Engineering.	http://www.nessi-europe.com/
ARTEMIS-IA	ARTEMIS Industry Association is the association for actors in Embedded Intelligent Systems within Europe. As private partner, the association represents its members - industry, SMEs, universities and research institutes - in ECSEL Joint Undertaking. ARTEMIS Industry Association continuously promotes the R&I interests of its members to the European Commission and the Public Authorities of the participating states.	https://artemis-ia.eu
ECLIPSE	The Eclipse Foundation provides to a global community of individuals and organizations with a mature, scalable, and business-friendly environment for open source software collaboration and innovation.	https://www.eclipse.org/
FIWARE	A market-ready open source software, combining components that enable the connection to IoT with Context Information Management and Big Data services in the Cloud.	https://www.fiware.org

Safety and cybersecurity		
ECSO	The European Cyber Security Organisation (ECSO) is the private counterpart to the European Commission in implementing the contractual Public-Private Partnership (cPPP) on cybersecurity. They unite a variety of European cybersecurity stakeholders across the EU Member States, the European Free Trade Association (EFTA) and H2020 Programme associated countries. ECSO's main goal is to develop a competitive European cybersecurity ecosystem, to support the protection of the European Digital Single Market with trusted cybersecurity solutions, and to contribute to the advancement of the European digital autonomy.	https://www.ecs-org.eu/
PSC Europe	The Public Safety Communications Europe Forum (PSCE) is a permanent autonomous organisation, working to foster excellence in the development and use of public safety communication and information management systems by consensus building. It was established as a result of a European Commission funded project in 2008. Since then, PSCE has evolved into an independent forum, where representatives of public safety user organisations, industry and research institutes can meet to discuss and exchange ideas and best practices, develop roadmaps and improve the future of public safety communications. PSCE ensures the continual improvement and evolution of public safety information and communication systems for the safety and security of the citizens.	https://www.psc-europe.eu/
EPTIS	ETPIS is an open cross ETP initiative focusing on industrial safety. It facilitates cooperation and enables constructive exchanges between industry, regulators in charge of health, safety and environmental protection, NGOs, trade unions and other social partners, and the research and innovation community.	https://www.eptis.org/
V2X: 5G-AA	The 5G Automotive Association (5GAA) is a global, cross-industry organisation of companies from the automotive, technology, and telecommunications industries (ICT), working together to develop end-to-end solutions for future mobility and transportation services.	https://5gaa.org/about-5gaa/about-us/
Projects		
5G Components		
5GRecords	The key challenge of <i>5G-RECORDS</i> is to explore the possibilities that new hardware devices and technologies may bring to the 5G ecosystem.	https://www.5g-records.eu/
TARANTO	The TARANTO project targets to break the technological barriers to the development of the next BiCMOS technology platforms, allowing the improvement of the performance of the HBT (Heterojunction Bipolar Transistors) with a much higher level of integration. The main technology objectives of this project will be to develop HBTs offering high maximum frequency (Fmax: 600GHz) built into very high density CMOS processes: 130 / 90nm for IFX, 55 / 28nm to ST, while IHP will work on the project to achieve maximum frequencies of 700GHz seeking compatibility with IFX and ST BiCMOS processes.	https://www.ecsel.eu/projects/taranto
Trial infrastructure		
5GASP	5GASP aims at shortening the idea-to-market process through the creation of a European testbed for SMEs that is fully automated and self-service, in order to foster rapid development and testing of new and innovative NetApps built using the 5G NFV based reference architecture. Building on top of existing physical infrastructures, 5GASP intends to focus on innovations related to the operation of experiments and tests across several domains, providing software support tools for Continuous Integration and Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) of VNFs in a secure & trusted environment for European SMEs capitalizing in the 5G market.	https://5g-ppp.eu/5gasp/

	5GASP targets the creation of an Open Source Software (OSS) repository and of a VNF marketplace targeting SMEs with OSS examples and building blocks, as well as the incubation of a community of NetApp developers assisted with tools and services that can enable an early validation and/or certification of products and services for 5G.	
5G-VINNI	5G-VINNI will accelerate the uptake of 5G in Europe by providing an end to end (E2E) facility that lowers the entry barrier for vertical industries to pilot use cases and supports the pilots as the infrastructure evolves.	https://www.5g-vinni.eu/concept-approach/
5G EVE	5G EVE is the European 5G validation platform for extensive trials. It is one of three 5G PPP infrastructure projects started on 1st July 2018. The goal is to implement and test advanced 5G infrastructures in Europe. The 5G-EVE concept is based on further developing and interconnecting existing European sites in Greece, Spain, France, and Italy to form a unique 5G end-to-end facility.	https://www.5g-eve.eu/
5GENESIS	It has the objective of validating the 5G network KPIs and verify the 5G technologies with an end-to-end approach. Towards this objective, a key challenge is to integrate all the highly diverse results and technologies from EU, global as well as internal (corporate) R&D projects, to “glue together” the 5G picture and unveil the potential of a truly full-stack, end-to-end 5G platform, able to meet the defined KPI targets.	https://5genesis.eu/
5GCroCo	5GCroCo will trial 5G technologies in the cross-border corridor along France, Germany and Luxembourg. In addition, 5GCroCo also aims at defining new business models that can be built on top of this unprecedented connectivity and service provisioning capacity. Ultimately, 5GCroCo will impact relevant standardization bodies from the telco and automotive industries.	https://5gcroco.eu/
5G Solutions	The 5G-SOLUTIONS main project objective is to conduct advanced field trials of innovative and thematically diverse digital services that require 5G capabilities and performance in the vertical domains of Factories of the Future, Smart Energy, Smart Cities, Smart Ports and Media & Entertainment, directly engaging with end-user actors, so as to validate the technological performance of 5G technology in successfully serving them, as well as validate the business models and potential of these use cases prior to commercial deployment.	https://5gsolutionsproject.eu/about/objectives/
Nanoelectronics		
NEREID12	The NEREID project (“NanoElectronics Roadmap for Europe: Identification and Dissemination”) is dedicated to map the future of European Nanoelectronics.	https://www.nereid-h2020.eu/
Processors		
EPI	The European Processor Initiative (EPI) is a project currently implemented under the first stage of the Framework Partnership Agreement signed by the Consortium with the European Commission (FPA: 800928), whose aim is to design and implement a roadmap for a new family of low-power European processors for extreme scale computing, high-performance Big-Data and a range of emerging applications.	https://www.european-processor-initiative.eu/project/epi/
Safety, cybersecurity and privacy		
VALU3S	The ECSEL JU project VALU3S aims to evaluate the state-of-the-art V&V methods and tools, and design a multi-domain framework to create a clear structure around the components and elements needed to conduct the V&V process. The main expected benefit of the framework is to reduce time and cost needed to verify and validate automated systems with respect to safety, cyber-security, and privacy requirements. This is done through identification and classification of evaluation methods, tools, environments and concepts for V&V of automated systems with respect to the mentioned requirements.	https://valu3s.eu/

ENABLE-S3	ENABLE-S3 will pave the way for accelerated application of highly automated and autonomous systems in the mobility domains automotive, aerospace, rail and maritime as well as in the health care domain. Virtual testing, verification and coverage-oriented test selection methods will enable validation with reasonable efforts. The resulting validation framework will ensure Europeans Industry competitiveness in the global race of automated systems with an expected market potential of 60B€ in 2025.	https://enable-s3.eu/
AI (Artificial Intelligence)		
5G-CLARITY	5G-CLARITY will develop and demonstrate a beyond 5G system for private networks integrating 5G, Wi-Fi, and LiFi technologies, and managed through AI based autonomic networking. It aims to be instrumental in order to secure the leadership of Europe in the growing markets of private 5G networks, and 5G for factory automation.	https://www.5gclarity.com
ECS		
Associations		
AENEAS	<p>AENEAS standing for Association for European NanoElectronics Activities, is an industrial Association, established in 2006, providing unparalleled networking opportunities, policy influence & supported access to funding to all types RD&I participants in the field of micro and nanoelectronics enabled components and systems.</p> <p>The object of the Association is to promote Research, Development and Innovation in order to strengthen the competitiveness of European industry across the electronics components and systems (ECS) value chain.</p>	https://aeneas-office.org
ARTEMIS-IA	<p>ARTEMIS Industry Association is the association for actors in Embedded Intelligent Systems within Europe. As private partner, the association represents its members - industry, SMEs, universities and research institutes - in ECSEL Joint Undertaking.</p> <p>ARTEMIS Industry Association continuously promotes the R&I interests of its members to the European Commission and the Public Authorities of the participating states.</p>	https://artemis-ia.eu
EPOSS	EPoSS, the European Technology Platform on Smart Systems Integration, is an industry-driven policy initiative, defining R&D and innovation needs as well as policy requirements related to Smart Systems Integration and integrated Micro and Nanosystems.	https://www.smart-systems-integration.org
EUREKA	Eureka, often abbreviated as E!, or Σ! is an intergovernmental organisation for research and development funding and coordination. Eureka is an open platform for international cooperation in innovation.	https://www.eurekanetwork.org/
SINANO Institute	: European Academic and Scientific Association for Nanoelectronics.	http://www.sinano.eu/
SEMI Europe	provides industry stewardship and engages our members to advance the interests of the global electronics design and manufacturing supply chain.	https://www.semi.org/eu
Silicon Europe	The European cluster alliance for innovative electronics & software technologies.	https://www.silicon-europe.eu/home/
DSP Valley	DSP Valley is a network for companies creating, applying, and adapting to electronic solutions and digital technologies.	https://breedingdigitalbusiness.com/

International Electronics Manufacturing Initiative (iNEMI)	The International Electronics Manufacturing Initiative (iNEMI) is a not-for-profit, highly efficient R&D consortium of approximately 90 leading electronics manufacturers, suppliers, associations, government agencies and universities.	https://www.inemi.org
Programmes		
KDT	The initiative aims to strengthen electronics value chains to ensure EU technological sovereignty in global competition. It builds on technological trends, including the generation of added value from systems integration, distribution of artificial intelligence applications across the cloud, the network edge and end devices, as well as new computing paradigms.	https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/11900-Research-&-innovation-partnership-for-key-digital-technologies-Horizon-Europe-programme-en
PENTA	PENTA supports projects along the Electronic Components & Systems (ECS) value chain, working with National Public Authorities to identify focus areas with common industrial and National interest. The PENTA programme is guided by the ECS Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA), a comprehensive document providing guidance on the challenges and opportunities for innovation along the electronics value chain.	https://penta-eureka.eu/
EURIPIDES2	is a EUREKA Cluster promoting the generation of innovative, industry-driven, pre-competitive R&D projects in the area of Smart Electronic Systems.	https://www.euripides-eureka.eu/
Telecom		
Associations		
5G IA	<p>The 5G Public Private Partnership (5G PPP) is the 5G collaborative research program that is organized as part of the European Commission’s Horizon 2020 program – The European Union Program for Research and Innovation. It is aimed at fostering industry-driven research, monitored by business-related, technological performance and societal KPIs. The 5G PPP will deliver solutions, architectures, technologies and standards for ubiquitous next-generation communication infrastructure over the coming decade.</p> <p>In the 5G PPP, the 5G IA represents the private side and the European Commission the public side. The 5G IA is committed to the advancement of 5G in Europe and to building global consensus on 5G. To this aim, the Association brings together a global industry community of telecoms & digital actors, such as operators, manufacturers, research institutes, universities, verticals, SMEs and ICT associations.</p>	https://5g-ia.eu/about/
NetWorld2020	NetWorld2020 is the European Technology Platform (ETP) for communications networks and services. Communications networks enable interaction between users of various types of equipment, either mobile or fixed. NetWorld2020 gathers players of the communications networks sector: industry leaders, innovative SMEs, and leading academic institutions. It was founded on 29 October 2013 by the former Net!Works and ISI ETPs. NetWorld2020 has more than 1,000 members coming from Industry, Research, and SMEs, as well as “Cooperation” members for external cooperation.	https://www.networld2020.eu/

ESA	The European Space Agency (ESA) is Europe’s gateway to space. Its mission is to shape the development of Europe’s space capability and ensure that investment in space continues to deliver benefits to the citizens of Europe and the world. Established in 1975, ESA works together with its 22 Member States to push the frontiers of science and technology, and promote economic growth in Europe.	http://www.esa.int/
EUREKA	Eureka, often abbreviated as E!, or Σ! is an intergovernmental organisation for research and development funding and coordination. Eureka is an open platform for international cooperation in innovation.	https://www.eurekanetwork.org/
GSM	The GSM Association is an industry organization that represents the interests of mobile network operators worldwide.	https://www.gsma.com/
Programmes		
SNS	The proposal for the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking adopted by the Commission today is part of the Single Basic Act establishing the set of nine Joint Undertakings under Horizon Europe. The proposal will now be discussed among Member States in the Council with a planned launch in autumn this year.	https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/europe-puts-forward-proposal-joint-undertaking-smart-networks-and-services-towards-6g
CELTIC-NEXT	CELTIC-NEXT is the EUREKA Cluster for next-generation communications enabling the digital society. CELTIC-NEXT stimulates and orchestrates international collaborative projects in the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) domain.	https://www.celticnext.eu/
Complementary industry & research		
AI (Artificial Intelligence)	Artificial intelligence (AI) is intelligence demonstrated by machines, unlike the natural intelligence displayed by humans and animals, which involves consciousness and emotionality. Artificial intelligence was founded as an academic discipline in 1955. The traditional problems (or goals) of AI research include reasoning, knowledge representation, planning, learning, natural language processing, perception and the ability to move and manipulate objects. AGI is among the field's long-term goals. Approaches include statistical methods, computational intelligence, and traditional symbolic AI. Many tools are used in AI, including versions of search and mathematical optimization, artificial neural networks, and methods based on statistics, probability and economics. The AI field draws upon computer science, information engineering, mathematics, psychology, linguistics, philosophy, and many other fields.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Artificial_intelligence
Cloud	Cloud computing is the on-demand availability of computer system resources, especially data storage (cloud storage) and computing power, without direct active management by the user. The term is generally used to describe data centers available to many users over the Internet. Large clouds, predominant today, often have functions distributed over multiple locations from central servers. If the connection to the user is relatively close, it may be designated an edge server. Clouds may be limited to a single organization (enterprise clouds, or be available to multiple organizations (public cloud). Cloud computing relies on sharing of resources to achieve coherence and economies of scale.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cloud_computing
HPC	High-performance computing (HPC) is the ability to process data and perform complex calculations at high speeds. To put it into perspective, a laptop or desktop with a 3 GHz processor can perform around 3 billion calculations per second.	https://www.netapp.com/data-storage/high-performance-computing/what-is-hpc/

	While that is much faster than any human can achieve, it pales in comparison to HPC solutions that can perform quadrillions of calculations per second.	
IoT	Things have evolved due to the convergence of multiple technologies, real-time analytics, machine learning, ubiquitous computing, commodity sensors, and embedded systems. Traditional fields of embedded systems, wireless sensor networks, control systems, automation (including home and building automation), and others all contribute to enabling the Internet of things. In the consumer market, IoT technology is most synonymous with products pertaining to the concept of the "smart home", including devices and appliances (such as lighting fixtures, thermostats, home security systems and cameras, and other home appliances) that support one or more common ecosystems, and can be controlled via devices associated with that ecosystem, such as smartphones and smart speakers. The IoT can also be used in healthcare systems.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internet_of_things
IIoT (Industrial IoT)	The industrial internet of things (IIoT) refers to interconnected sensors, instruments, and other devices networked together with computers' industrial applications, including manufacturing and energy management. This connectivity allows for data collection, exchange, and analysis, potentially facilitating improvements in productivity and efficiency as well as other economic benefits. The IIoT is an evolution of a distributed control system (DCS) that allows for a higher degree of automation by using cloud computing to refine and optimize the process controls.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Industrial_internet_of_things
Photonics	Photonics is the physical science and application of light (photon) generation, detection, and manipulation through emission, transmission, modulation, signal processing, switching, amplification, and sensing. Though covering all light's technical applications over the whole spectrum, most photonic applications are in the range of visible and near-infrared light. The term photonics developed as an outgrowth of the first practical semiconductor light emitters invented in the early 1960s and optical fibers developed in the 1970s.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Photonics
Big Data	Big data is a field that treats ways to analyze, systematically extract information from, or otherwise deal with data sets that are too large or complex to be dealt with by traditional data-processing application software. Data with many fields (columns) offer greater statistical power, while data with higher complexity (more attributes or columns) may lead to a higher false discovery rate. Big data analysis challenges include capturing data, data storage, data analysis, search, sharing, transfer, visualization, querying, updating, information privacy, and data source. Big data was originally associated with three key concepts: volume, variety, and velocity. The analysis of big data presents challenges in sampling, and thus previously allowing for only observations and sampling. Therefore, big data often includes data with sizes that exceed the capacity of traditional software to process within an acceptable time and value.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Big_data
Robotics	Robotics is an interdisciplinary field that integrates computer science and engineering. Robotics involves design, construction, operation, and use of robots. The goal of robotics is to design machines that can help and assist humans. Robotics integrates fields of mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, information engineering, mechatronics, electronics, bioengineering, computer engineering, control engineering, software engineering, mathematics, among others.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Robotics

Software	Software is a collection of instructions and data that tell a computer how to work. This is in contrast to physical hardware, from which the system is built and actually performs the work. In computer science and software engineering, computer software is all information processed by computer systems, including programs and data. Computer software includes computer programs, libraries and related non-executable data, such as online documentation or digital media. Computer hardware and software require each other and neither can be realistically used on its own.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Software
Embedded software	Embedded software is computer software, written to control machines or devices that are not typically thought of as computers, commonly known as embedded systems. It is typically specialized for the particular hardware that it runs on and has time and memory constraints. This term is sometimes used interchangeably with firmware. A precise and stable characteristic feature is that no or not all functions of embedded software are initiated/controlled via a human interface, but through machine-interfaces instead.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Embedded_software
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) is communication between a vehicle and any entity that may affect, or may be affected by, the vehicle. It is a vehicular communication system that incorporates other more specific types of communication as V2I (vehicle-to-infrastructure), V2N (vehicle-to-network), V2V (vehicle-to-vehicle), V2P (vehicle-to-pedestrian), V2D (vehicle-to-device) and V2G (vehicle-to-grid).	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vehicle-to-everything
5G/6G Policy Makers and Financing Bodies		
Policy makers	A policy maker is a member of a government department, legislature, or other organization who is responsible for making new rules, laws, etc.	http://dictionary.cambridge.org/us/dictionary/english/policymaker
CEPT	CEPT is the European Conference of Postal and Telecommunications Administrations. Its activities include co-operation on commercial, operational, regulatory and technical standardisation issues. The CEPT was established in 1959 by 19 countries, which expanded to 26 during its first ten years. Original members were the monopoly-holding postal and telecommunications administrations. Today 48 countries are members of the CEPT.	http://www.cept.org
EC (European Commission)	The European Commission (EC) is the European Union's executive body. It represents the interests of the European Union as a whole (not the interests of individual countries). The EC is responsible for policies in the areas that it covers e.g. trade.	http://ec.europa.eu/about/index_en.htm , https://ec.europa.eu/trade/policy/policy-making/
ECC (PT1)	The Electronic Communications Committee (ECC) is a body of national regulators operating at the European level to identify and realise the benefits of harmonised approaches to spectrum management across the CEPT* countries The ECC Project Team 1 (PT1) is responsible for implementing the Wireless Access Policy for Electronic Communications Services (WAPECS) concept (the new European flexible approach based on technology and service neutral regulation) for mobile and fixed communications networks (MFCN).	http://www.cept.org/ec/who-we-are/participation-in-ecc-work/ , http://www.cept.org/ec/groups/ecc/ecc-pt1/client/introduction/
ITU	The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) is the United Nations (UN) specialized agency for information and communication (ICT) technologies. ITU	http://www.itu.int

	allocates global radio spectrum and satellite orbits, develop the technical standards that ensure networks and technologies seamlessly interconnect, and strive to improve access to ICTs to underserved communities worldwide.	
National regulators e.g. OFCOM	National regulators are organisations e.g. agencies that regulate telecommunications services in each country / Member State. One example is OFCOM that is the communications regulator in the UK to regulate the TV, radio and video on demand sectors, fixed line telecoms, mobiles, postal services, plus the airwaves over which wireless devices operate.	http://www.ofcom.org.uk/about/what-is-ofcom/
ITU-R WP5D	ITU-R (International Telecommunication Union – Radiocommunication Sector) is an organisation of United Nations. The mission of the ITU Radiocommunication Sector is, inter alia, to ensure rational, equitable, efficient and economical use of the radio-frequency spectrum by all radiocommunication services, including those using satellite orbits, and to carry out studies and adopt recommendations on radiocommunication matters. Working Party 5D (WP 5D) - IMT Systems is responsible for the overall radio system aspects of International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT) systems, comprising the IMT-2000, IMT-Advanced and IMT for 2020 and beyond.	https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-R/Pages/default.aspx ; https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-R/study-groups/rsg5/rwp5d/Pages/default.aspx
Vertical policy makers e.g. EBU	Vertical policy makers are <i>policy makers</i> * that are acting in a specific vertical sector e.g. automotive, energy, health, media... The European Broadcasting Union (EBU) is the world's leading alliance of public service media (PSM).	https://www.ebu.ch
ESA	The European Space Agency (ESA) is Europe's gateway to space. Its mission is to shape the development of Europe's space capability and ensure that investment in space continues to deliver benefits to the citizens of Europe and the world. Established in 1975, ESA works together with its 22 Member States to push the frontiers of science and technology, and promote economic growth in Europe.	http://www.esa.int/
ENISA	The European Union Agency for Cybersecurity[1] – self-designation ENISA from the abbreviation of its original name – is an agency of the European Union. It is fully operational since September 1, 2005. The Agency is located in Athens, Greece and has a second office in Heraklion, Greece.	https://www.enisa.europa.eu/
Financing bodies		
- Public funding -		
EC		
EC (European Commission)	The European Commission (EC) is the European Union's executive body. It represents the interests of the European Union as a whole (not the interests of individual countries). The EC is funding various programmes and initiatives, including but not limited to the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation.	http://ec.europa.eu/about/index_en.htm ; https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en
Horizon Europe programmes for SNS	Horizon Europe is the EU's key funding programme for research and innovation.	https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en

Connecting Europe Facility (CEF)	is a key EU funding instrument to promote growth, jobs and competitiveness through targeted infrastructure investment at European level. It supports the development of high performing, sustainable and efficiently interconnected trans-European networks in the fields of transport, energy and digital services. CEF investments fill the missing links in Europe's energy, transport and digital backbone.	https://ec.europa.eu/inea/en/connecting-europe-facility
Cohesion fund (CF)	The Cohesion Fund is aimed at Member States whose Gross National Income (GNI) per inhabitant is less than 90 % of the EU average. It aims to reduce economic and social disparities and to promote sustainable development.	https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/funding/cohesion-fund/
National, Regional and Local Public Authorities and agencies incharge of supporting 5G/6G and of components		
bpiFrance	Banque publique d'investissement, Public Investment Bank, also known as Bpifrance, (BPI Groupe S.A.) is a French public investment bank.	https://www.bpifrance.fr/
KfW	The KfW, formerly KfW Bankengruppe ("banking group"), is a German state-owned investment and development bank, based in Frankfurt. As of 2014, it is the world's largest national development bank and as of 2018 Germany's third largest bank by balance sheet.	https://www.kfw.de/
Netherlands Enterprise Agency	It is a government agency which operates under the auspices of the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy. Its activities are commissioned by the various Dutch ministries and the European Union.	https://english.rvo.nl/
Sowalfin Novallia Belgium	Since 2009, NOVALLIA, a subsidiary of the SOWALFIN Group, has been putting its expertise in innovation financing at the service of Walloon VSEs and SMEs.	http://www.novallia.be/
Belgium VLAIO	The Agency for Innovation and Entrepreneurship (VLAIO) is a governmental organisation of the Flemish government for all entrepreneurs in Flanders. In 2016, Enterprise Flanders and the company activities of IWT were merged into VLAIO. The research activities of IWT were taken over by the Flemish Research Council (FWO).The mission of VLAIO is to stimulate and support innovation and entrepreneurship and to contribute to a favourable business-climate in Flanders.	https://www.vlaio.be/nl
innoviris	INNOVIRIS is a public agency established in 2004 answering directly to the regional minister with responsibility for scientific research. Its mission is to support and encourage research, development and innovation in and for Brussels through the funding of innovative projects of companies, research organisations and the non-profit sector.	https://innoviris.brussels/
-Private investors-		
Target partners	Target Partners is a European venture capital fund. Target Partners targets have activities in the IT domain.	https://www.targetpartners.de/
Bullnet Capital	Spanish independent Venture Capital Firm, specialized in high technology start-ups. Bullnet targets IP companies and those of R&D background.	http://www.bullnetcapital.com/
Silicon Valley Bank	Silicon Valley Bank, a subsidiary of SVB Financial Group, is a U.S.-based high-tech commercial bank. The bank has helped fund more than 30,000 start-ups. SVB is on the list of largest banks in the United States. It's the biggest bank in Silicon	https://www.svb.com/#

	Valley. Innovative companies are privileged targets without any restriction on their activity sector. Photonics investment example: Sabeus Photonic.	
Kreos Capital	Kreos is a financing body with the single mission of pioneering unique financing solutions for high-growth companies across Europe and Israel, in a variety of industry sectors and located in 17 countries. The firm seeks to invest in companies that are backed by an established VC. Photonics and semiconductors investment examples: Rockley, Crocus.	http://www.kreoscapital.com/
5G / 6G Standards Organisations		
Standardisation organisations	A Standardization organization (or standards body, Standards Developing Organization (SDO), or Standards Setting Organization (SSO)) is an organization whose primary activities are developing, coordinating, promulgating, revising, amending, reissuing, interpreting, or otherwise producing technical standards that are intended to address the needs of some relatively wide base of affected adopters.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Standards_organization
3GPP	The 3 rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) unites seven telecommunications Standard Development Organizations (ARIB, ATIS, CCSA, ETSI, TSDSI, TTA, TTC), known as “Organizational Partners” and provides their members with a stable environment to produce the Reports and Specifications that define 3GPP technologies.	http://www.3gpp.org/
ASTM	ASTM International, formerly known as American Society for Testing and Materials, is an international standards organization that develops and publishes voluntary consensus technical standards for a wide range of materials, products, systems, and services. Some 12,575 ASTM voluntary consensus standards operate globally.	https://www.astm.org/
CEN CENELEC	CEN (Comité Européen de Normalisation; European Committee for Standardization) and CENELEC (Comité Européen de Normalisation Électrotechnique; European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization) are business catalysts in Europe, removing trade barriers for European industry and consumers. Their mission is to foster the European economy in global trading, the welfare of European citizens and the environment. Through their services they provide platforms for the development of European Standards and other technical specs.	https://www.cenelec.eu/Pages/default.aspx
ECMA International	Is an industry association dedicated to the standardization of information and communication systems	https://www.ecma-international.org/
ETSI (OSM)	The European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), a non-profit organization, produces globally applicable standards for Information and Communications Technologies (ICT), including fixed, mobile, radio, converged, broadcast and Internet technologies. The standards enable the technologies on which business and society rely. For example, standards for GSM™, DECT™, Smart Cards and electronic signatures have helped to revolutionize modern life all over the world. More than 800 member organizations worldwide, drawn from 66 countries and five continents. Members include the world’s leading companies and innovative R&D organizations. Open Source MANO (OSM) is delivering an open source Management and Orchestration (MANO) stack aligned with ETSI NFV Information Models. As a community-led community, OSM offers a production-quality MANO stack that meets operators' requirements for commercial NFV deployments.	http://www.etsi.org , https://osm.etsi.org/
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE), is the world’s largest professional association dedicated to advancing technological innovation and excellence for the benefit of humanity. The IEEE covers technology areas ranging from	https://www.ieee.org

	aerospace systems, computers and telecommunications to biomedical engineering, electric power and consumer electronics.	
IET	The Institution of Engineering and Technology (IET) is a multidisciplinary professional engineering institution. The IET was formed in 2006 from two separate institutions: the Institution of Electrical Engineers (IEE), dating back to 1871, and the Institution of Incorporated Engineers (IIE) dating back to 1884. Its worldwide membership is currently in excess of 168,000. The mission of IET is: “We are the IET and we inspire, inform and influence the global engineering community to engineer a better world. As a diverse home across engineering and technology, we share knowledge that helps make better sense of the world in order to solve the challenges that matter. It’s why we are uniquely placed to champion engineering.”	https://www.theiet.org/
IETF/IRTF	The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) is a large open international community of network designers, operators, vendors, and researchers concerned with the evolution of the Internet architecture and the smooth operation of the Internet. It is open to any interested individual with no formal membership or membership requirements. All participants and managers are volunteers, though their work is usually funded by their employers or sponsors. The Internet Research Task Force (IRTF) focuses on longer term research issues related to the Internet while the parallel organization, the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), focuses on the shorter-term issues of engineering and standards making. The IRTF promotes research of importance to the evolution of the Internet by creating focused, long-term Research Groups working on topics related to Internet protocols, applications, architecture and technology.	https://www.ietf.org/
ISO/IEC	The International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is an international standard-setting body composed of representatives from various national standards organizations. Founded on 23 February 1947, the organization promotes worldwide proprietary, industrial, and commercial standards. It is headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland, and works in 164 countries. It was one of the first organizations granted general consultative status with the United Nations Economic and Social Council. ISO has formed two joint committees with the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) to develop standards and terminology in the areas of electrical and electronic related technologies: ISO/IEC Joint Technical Committee 1 (JTC 1) was created in 1987 to "develop, maintain, promote and facilitate IT standards", where IT refers to information technology; and ISO/IEC Joint Technical Committee 2 (JTC 2), created in 2009 for the purpose of "standardization in the field of energy efficiency and renewable energy sources".	https://www.iso.org/ ; https://www.iec.ch/
ITU(-T)	ITU-T is one of the three sectors of <i>ITU*</i> . It formulates recommendations for standardizing telecommunication operations worldwide.	https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/
MEF	MEF, founded in 2001 as the Metro Ethernet Forum is a non-profit international industry consortium, dedicated to adoption of assured services orchestrated across a global ecosystem of automated networks. MEF was originally dedicated to Carrier Ethernet networks and services, but is no longer referred to as the "Metro Ethernet Forum" because the work of MEF is now much broader in scope, and includes Optical, Carrier Ethernet, IP, SD-WAN Services and Cloud Services, as well as orchestration of the service lifecycle. However, it retains the name "MEF" and "MEF Forum". The forum is composed of service providers, incumbent local exchange carriers, network equipment vendors, and other networking companies that share an interest in connectivity services. There are over 200 MEF members currently. Membership varies for many reasons including mergers and acquisitions of member companies.	https://www.o-ran.org/
TM Forum	TM Forum is a global industry association for service providers and their suppliers in the telecommunications industry. Members include communications and	www.tmforum.org

	digital service providers, telephone companies, cable operators, network operators, cloud providers, digital infrastructure providers, software suppliers, equipment suppliers, systems integrators and management consultancies. The Forum has over 850 member companies, including ten of the top ten world's largest telecommunications service providers, that collectively generate US\$2 trillion in revenue and serve five billion customers across 180 countries.	
IEEE-SA	The Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Standards Association (IEEE SA) is an Operating Unit within IEEE that develops global standards in a broad range of industries, including: power and energy, artificial intelligence systems, internet of things, consumer technology and consumer electronics, biomedical and health care, learning technology, information technology and robotics, telecommunication and home automation, automotive, transportation, home automation, nanotechnology, information assurance, emerging technologies, and many more.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IEEE_Standards_Association
Other standard-related and open source organisations		
POSC	Is a global, nonprofit member organization that shall promote the development of open specifications to be used as standards for enabling the interoperability of data, software and related matters.	https://www.posccaesar.org/
DEXPI	The objective of the DEXPI Initiative is to develop and promote a general data exchange standard for the process industry, covering all phases of the lifecycle of a (petro-)chemical plant, ranging from specification of functional requirements to assets in operation. Currently, the focus of the DEXPI initiative is the exchange of <i>Piping and Instrumentation diagrams</i> (P&IDs).	https://dexpi.org/
OW2	Is a unique European ecosystem of open source people and organizations.	https://www.ow2.org/
Open Forum Europe	OpenForum Europe (OFE) is a European open source software and open standard not-for-profit organisation advocating for interoperability in technology. Its key objective is to contribute to achieve an open and competitive Digital ecosystem in Europe.	https://open-forumeurope.org/about-ofe/
FSFE	Free Software Foundation Europe (FSFE) is a charity that empowers users to control technology.	https://fsfe.org/
FOSDEM	FOSDEM is a free and Open source Software Developers' European Meeting is a non-commercial, volunteer-organized European event centered on free and open-source software development. It is aimed at developers and anyone interested in the free and open-source software movement.	https://fosdem.org/2021/
Data Space Connector	The Dataspace Connector is an open-source system for sovereign data exchange based on usage policies within and cross-organizational.	https://www.dataspace-connector.io/
MulteFire	The MulteFire Alliance is an independent, diverse, and international member-driven consortium defining and promoting MulteFire – a cellular-based technology for operating in unlicensed and shared spectrum. The purpose is to support the common interests of members, developers and users in the application of LTE and next generation mobile cellular technology—such as 5G New Radio—in configurations that use only unlicensed or shared radio spectrum. The MulteFire Alliance has grown to more than 40 members. The organization is open to any company with an interest in advancing LTE and cellular technology in unlicensed and shared spectrum.	https://www.multe-fire.org/

GUTMA	The Global UTM Association (GUTMA) is a non-profit consortium of worldwide Unmanned Aircraft Systems Traffic Management (UTM) stakeholders. Its purpose is to foster the safe, secure and efficient integration of drones in national airspace systems. Its mission is to support and accelerate the transparent implementation of globally interoperable UTM systems. GUTMA members collaborate remotely.	https://gutma.org/
IDSA	International Data Space Association: Digital transformation is a key factor for the success of companies worldwide. IDSA ensure that the special economic interests of business are specifically integrated into the research work of International Data Space. Companies can access the results of the research project on International Data Spaces on the website so they can implement these results in their own way.	https://www.internationaldataspaces.org/
O-RAN	The O-RAN Alliance was founded by operators to clearly define requirements and help build a supply chain eco-system to realize its objectives. O-RAN Alliance members and contributors have committed to evolving radio access networks around the world.	https://www.o-ran.org/
USERS OF THE COREnect TECHNOLOGIES		
Policy makers and financing bodies		
Policy makers		
CEPT	CEPT is the European Conference of Postal and Telecommunications Administrations. Its activities include co-operation on commercial, operational, regulatory and technical standardisation issues. The CEPT was established in 1959 by 19 countries, which expanded to 26 during its first ten years. Original members were the monopoly-holding postal and telecommunications administrations. Today 48 countries are members of the CEPT.	http://www.cept.org
EC	The European Commission (EC) is the European Union's executive body. It represents the interests of the European Union as a whole (not the interests of individual countries). The EC is responsible for policies in the areas that it covers e.g. trade.	http://ec.europa.eu/about/index_en.htm , https://ec.europa.eu/trade/policy/policy-making/
ECC	The European Consumer Centres Network (ECC-Net) is an EU-wide network. There is a national contact point called European Consumer Centre (ECC) in all 28 EU Member States, in Iceland and Norway. ECCs provide consumers with information about the opportunities and risks of the European Single Market and also regarding cross-border consumer topics, such as travel, various services, and the purchase of goods and services. The ECC-Net is staffed by legal experts who assist consumers free of charge to solve any dispute that may arise with enterprises based in another EU country, Norway, or Iceland. The ECCs are co-financed by the European Commission and national governments aiming to protect consumer rights and ensure that every EU citizen may take full advantage of the European Single Market. Depending on the formal structure some ECCs are hosted by non-governmental organizations (NGOs), governmental bodies, or independent organizations.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/European_Consumer_Centres_Network
ECC PT1	The Electronic Communications Committee (ECC) is a body of national regulators operating at the European level to identify and realise the benefits of harmonised approaches to spectrum management across the CEPT* countries. The ECC Project Team 1 (PT1) is responsible for implementing the Wireless Access Policy for Electronic Communications Services (WAPECS) concept (the new European flexible approach based on technology and service neutral regulation) for mobile and fixed communications networks (MFCN).	http://www.cept.org/ec/who-we-are/participation-in-ecc-work/ , http://www.cept.org/ec/groups/ecc/ecc-pt1/client/introduction/

ITU	The International Telecommunication Union (ITU) is the United Nations (UN) specialized agency for information and communication (ICT) technologies. ITU allocates global radio spectrum and satellite orbits, develop the technical standards that ensure networks and technologies seamlessly interconnect, and strive to improve access to ICTs to underserved communities worldwide.	http://www.itu.int
ITU-R WP5D	WP 5D is responsible for the overall radio system aspects of International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT) systems, comprising IMT-2000, IMT-Advanced, IMT-2020 and IMT for 2030 and beyond.	https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-R/study-groups/rsg5/rwp5d/Pages/default.aspx
National regulators, e.g. OFCOM	National regulators are organisations e.g. agencies that regulate telecommunications services in each country / Member State. One example is OFCOM that is the communications regulator in the UK to regulate the TV, radio and video on demand sectors, fixed line telecoms, mobiles, postal services, plus the airwaves over which wireless devices operate.	http://www.ofcom.org.uk/about/what-is-ofcom/
Vertical policy makers e.g. EBU	Vertical policy makers are <i>policy makers</i> * that are acting in a specific vertical sector e.g. automotive, energy, health, media... The European Broadcasting Union (EBU) is the world's leading alliance of public service media (PSM).	https://www.ebu.ch
Financing bodies		
European regional development fund (ERDF)	The ERDF aims to strengthen economic and social cohesion in the European Union by correcting imbalances between its regions.	https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/funding/erdf/
EARFD	European agricultural fund for rural development. Through financial instruments, the EAFRD acts as a source for loans, microcredits, guarantees and equities, available to recipients in agriculture, forestry and rural areas who are undertaking financially viable projects that support the priorities of the EAFRD.	https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/regional-innovation-monitor/organisation/brussels-institute-research-and-innovation-innoviris
EIB (European Investment Bank)	The European Investment Bank is the lending arm of the European Union. We are the biggest multilateral financial institution in the world and one of the largest providers of climate finance.	https://www.eib.org/en/index.htm
World Health Organization (WHO)	The World Health Organization (WHO) is a specialized agency of the United Nations responsible for international public health. The WHO Constitution, which establishes the agency's governing structure and principles, states its main objective as "the attainment by all peoples of the highest possible level of health". It is headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland, with six semi-autonomous regional offices and 150 field offices worldwide.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/World_Health_Organization
European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF)	EMFF helps fishers to adopt sustainable fishing practices and coastal communities to diversify their economies, improving quality of life along European coasts.	https://ec.europa.eu/oceans-and-fisheries/index_en
5G/6G COREnect Technology Users / Intermediaries*		

Vertical device vendors	Vertical manufacturing can take place any time a manufacturer takes control of elements that are closer to its suppliers or customers than its main manufacturing operation. Control of value stream elements toward the supplier is known as upstream, or backward, integration.	https://smallbusiness.chron.com/vertical-manufacturing-mean-20892.html
Modem	A modulator-demodulator, or simply a modem, is a hardware device that converts data from a digital format, intended for communication directly between devices with specialized wiring, into one suitable for a transmission medium such as telephone lines or radio. A modem modulates one or more carrier wave signals to encode digital information for transmission, and demodulates signals to decode the transmitted information. The goal is to produce a signal that can be transmitted easily and decoded reliably to reproduce the original digital data.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Modem
IoT specialised end device vendors	Vendor of the Internet of things (IoT) which is the network of physical objects— a.k.a. "things"—that are embedded with sensors, software, and other technologies for the purpose of connecting and exchanging data with other devices and systems over the Internet	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internet_of_things
Specialised intermediaries	Specialized Intermediaries are involved in the distribution channel to perform a specific duty and typically do not get involved with the core business practices. Advertising agencies, Marketing research firms, and insurance companies are examples of these intermediaries.	https://www.melinakmiller.com/the-four-types-of-marketing-intermediaries/
Industrial Applications – connected smart fab	Smart-Fab is a disposable fabric substitute, which receives the characteristics of regular woven cloth during the unique non-woven fabric manufacturing process. Smart-Fab is made of recyclable polypropylene.	
Vertical Industry		
Mobility	Mobility is the industry of transporting people and goods. ... This is due to advances in multi-modal transport (e.g., changing vehicles mid-journey) and applications of software (e.g., autonomous driving).	https://www.toptal.com/finance/industry/future-of-mobility
Automotive	The automotive industry comprises a wide range of companies and organizations involved in the design, development, manufacturing, marketing, and selling of motor vehicles.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Automotive_industry
Rail	A means of transferring passengers and goods on wheeled vehicles running on rails. Examples include passenger and commuter trains (e.g. suburban and airport shuttle services), freight trains (goods). Future rail use cases enabled by 5G include connected devices, operations, passengers and interventions.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Rail_transport https://cdn.net-workrail.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/05/Enabling-5G-for-the-rail.pdf
Maritime	A means of transport for people (passengers) and goods (cargo) by sea, lakes, canals and rivers across any distance for commercial, recreational or military purposes. 5G-enabled applications include the introduction of smart drones for real-time monitoring, ship-shore communication for vessel traffic management and just-in-time operations, as well as the adoption of autonomous vessels with low latency connectivity for remote operation.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maritime_transport https://global5g.org/online-tool-standards-tracker/maritime-technical-viewpoints-5g
shared service provider	Shared services is the provision of a service by one part of an organization or group, where that service had previously been found, in more than one part of the organization or group. Thus the funding and resourcing of the service is	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shared_services

	shared and the providing department effectively becomes an internal service provider.	
Infrastructure		
Telecom	Telecommunication is the transmission of information by various types of technologies over wire, radio, optical or other electromagnetic systems ¹ It has its origin in the desire of humans for communication over a distance greater than that feasible with the human voice, but with a similar scale of expediency; thus, slow systems (such as postal mail) are excluded from the field.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Telecommunication
Road transport monitoring	It is an intelligent transportation system (ITS) with advanced application which aims to provide innovative services relating to different modes of monitoring transport and traffic management and enable users to be better informed and make safer, more coordinated, and 'smarter' use of transport networks.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Intelligent_transportation_system
Media		
Studios	A studio is an artist or worker's workroom. This can be for the purpose of acting, architecture, painting, pottery (ceramics), sculpture, origami, woodworking, scrapbooking, photography, graphic design, filmmaking, animation, industrial design, radio or television production broadcasting or the making of music.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Studio
Broadcasters	A broadcasting organization, one responsible for audio and video content and/or their transmission. The European Broadcasting Union (EBU; French: Union européenne de radio-télévision, UER; German: Europäische Rundfunkunion, ERU) is an alliance of public service media organisations, established on 12 February 1950. The organisation is made up of 116 member organisations in 56 countries,[2] and 34 associate members from a further 21 countries.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/European_Broadcasting_Union
Content providers	A service provider (SP) provides organizations with consulting, legal, real estate, communications, storage, processing. Although a service provider can be an organizational sub-unit, it is usually a third party or outsourced supplier, including telecommunications service providers (TSPs), application service providers (ASPs), storage service providers (SSPs), and internet service providers (ISPs).	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Service_provider
Media service providers	Satellite television is a service that delivers television programming to viewers by relaying it from a communications satellite orbiting the Earth directly to the viewer's location.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Satellite_television
Health and wellbeing		
Pharmaceutical companies	A pharmaceutical company, or drug company, is a commercial business licensed to research, develop, market and/or distribute drugs, most commonly in the context of healthcare. They can deal in generic and/or brand medications. They are subject to a variety of laws and regulations regarding the patenting, testing and marketing of drugs, particularly prescription drugs.	https://www.sciencedaily.com/terms/pharmaceutical_company.htm
Emergency services	Primary emergency services are police, fire and emergency medical services (EMS). Core services are provided by a government department (e.g. law enforcement agency, Ministry of Interior) or private body. Also referred to as First Responders.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Emergency_service
Insurance companies	A company that provides and sells insurance as a form of risk management. The entity providing insurance is known as an insurer, insurance company, insurance carrier or underwriter. A person or entity who buys insurance is known as an insured or as a policyholder.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Insurance
Digital industry		

Factories of the future	The Factory of the Future has an evolving definition, including different names such as Smart Manufacturing, Industry 4.0 or the Digital Enterprise. While the terms vary, some elements are always in common: it is the product of fast-changing disruptive technologies, whereby information technology and operational technology are both introducing drastic innovations.	https://www.industry-week.com/technology-and-iiot/emerging-technologies/article/21972483/preparing-for-the-factory-of-the-future
Manufacturing	Manufacturing is the production of products for use or sale using labor and machines, tools, chemical or biological processing or formulation and is the essence of secondary industry. The term may refer to a range of human activity from handicraft to high tech but is most commonly applied to industrial design, in which raw materials from primary industry are transformed into finished goods on a large scale.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Manufacturing
Logistics	The movement of humans, animals and goods from one location to another by air, land (rail and road), water, cable, pipeline and space requiring infrastructure, vehicles and operation. Logistics is the management of the flow of things between the point of origin and consumption, including asset tracking across diverse transport modes.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Transport https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Logistics
Digital society		https://en.wikipedia.org/
Consumers	A consumer is one that buys goods for consumption and not for resale or commercial purpose. The consumer is an individual who pays some amount of money for the thing required to consume goods and services.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Consumer
Smart cities	A smart city is a city performing well in 6 characteristics, built on the “smart” combination of endowments and activities of self-decisive, independent and aware citizens. The 6 characteristics are the following: Smart Economy; Smart Mobility; Smart Governance; Smart Living; Smart People; Smart Environment. A Smart city could use some services and Infrastructures provided by the 5G PPP projects, make these services available to the <i>developers</i> *.	Giffinger, et.al, 2007
Tourism	People traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure and not less than 24 hours, business and other purposes.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tourism
Energy	The electric power industry covers the generation, transmission, distribution and sale of electric power to the general public and industry.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electric_power_industry
Power companies	Electric power companies own the whole infrastructure from generating stations to transmission and distribution infrastructure.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electric_power_industry
Utilities	An electric utility is a company in the electric power industry (often a public utility) that engages in electricity generation and distribution of electricity for sale generally in a regulated market. The electrical utility industry is a major provider of energy in most countries.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electric_utility
Smart grid operators	Smart grid technology provides the means for grid operators to match up supply and demand at a local level. With the development of decentralised generation from wind and solar this flexible approach can reduce the need for network infrastructure to move power around the system and for backup generation capacity.	https://www.regen.co.uk/smart-grids-and-the-role-of-the-dso/
Public safety		

Police	A constituted body of persons empowered by a state to enforce the law, to ensure the safety, health and possessions of citizens, and to prevent crime and civil disorder.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Police
Rescue and fire departments	A fire and rescue authority is a statutory body made up of a committee of local councillors which oversees the policy and service delivery of a fire and rescue service.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fire_authority
Ambulance	A medically equipped vehicle which transports patients to treatment facilities, such as hospitals. In some instances, out-of-hospital medical care is provided to the patient.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ambulance
Vertical initiatives & Projects		
Initiatives		
Mobility		
ERTRAC	ERTRAC is the European Road Transport Research Advisory Council.	https://www.ertrac.org/
ERRAC	Strategic Rail Research and Innovation Agenda	http://errac.org
5GACIA	5G-ACIA is a global forum for shaping 5G in the industrial domain. The paramount objective of 5G-ACIA is to ensure the best possible applicability of 5G technology for connected industries, in particular the manufacturing and process industries.	https://www.5g-acia.org/
5G-AA	The 5G Automotive Association (5GAA) is a global, cross-industry organisation of companies from the automotive, technology, and telecommunications industries (ICT), working together to develop end-to-end solutions for future mobility and transportation services.	https://5gaa.org/about-5gaa/about-us/
ERTICO	ERTICO – ITS (Intelligent Transport Systems and Services) Europe is a public-private partnership of 120 companies and organisations representing service providers, suppliers, traffic and transport industry, research, public authorities, user organisations, mobile network operators, and vehicle manufacturers. ERTICO’s work focuses on Connected & Automated Driving, Urban Mobility, Clean Mobility, and Transport & Logistics.	https://ertico.com/
EATA	European Automotive Telecom Alliance	https://eata.be/
CCAM	Cooperative, connected and automated mobility	https://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/its/c-its_en
UIC	UIC, the worldwide professional association representing the railway sector and promoting rail transport. UIC leads an innovative and dynamic sector, helping Members find continuing success and opportunities.	https://uic.org/about/about-uic/
ACEA	The European Automobile Manufacturers’ Association, or ACEA, unites Europe’s 15 major car, truck, van and bus makers.	https://www.acea.auto/
IRU	IRU is the world road transport organisation. We represent the entire industry – bus, coach, truck and taxi, and drive the sustainable mobility of people and goods across the planet.	https://www.iru.org
Mobility.E Lighthouse	The Mobility.E Lighthouse is an initiative of the ECSEL JU, a public-private partnership launched by the EC. Its goal is to promote research and development in the field of electronics.	https://www.mobilitye.eu/
EGVIA	European Green Vehicle Initiative Association.	https://egvi.eu/

EGCI	European Green Cars Initiative.	https://www.egvi.eu
Media		
NEM	The NEM Initiative (New European Media Initiative) was established as one of the European Technology Platform under the Seventh Framework Programme, aiming at fostering the convergence between consumer electronics, broadcasting and telecoms in order to develop the emerging business sector of networked and electronic media. In order to respond to new need and requirements of the Horizon 2020 programme, the NEM initiative enlarged its focus towards creative industries and changed its name from Networked an Electronic Media Initiative to New European Media, dealing with Connected, Converging and Interactive Media & Creative Industries, driving the future of digital experience. The NEM constituency includes all major European organisations working in the networked and electronic media area, including content providers, creative industries, broadcasters, network equipment manufacturers, network operators and service providers, academia, standardisation bodies and government institutions. The NEM Initiative is supporting Europe’s activities on the Future Internet and is actively contributing to the definition of the related research and innovation areas.	https://nem-initiative.org/
EBU	The European Broadcasting Union (EBU) is the world’s leading alliance of public service media (PSM), with 116 member organizations in 56 countries and has an additional 34 Associates in Asia, Africa, Australasia and the Americas. EBU’s Members operate nearly 2,000 television, radio and online channels and services, and offer a wealth of content across other platforms. Together they reach an audience of more than one billion people around the world, broadcasting in more than 160 languages. The EBU strives to secure a sustainable future for public service media.	https://www.ebu.ch/home
Health and Wellbeing		
ECHalliance	The European Connected Health Alliance (ECHalliance) facilitates multi-stakeholder connections around ecosystems, driving sustainable change and disruption in the delivery of health and social care. The global network of Digital Health Alliances connects 78 countries and 4.4 billion people (Europe, USA, Canada, China, Africa, Asia, the Caribbean and Americas and the Pacific), and involves a community of over 16,500 experts. The Digital Health Observatory (DHO) and The Digital Health Society (DHS) movement facilitate and promote the transfer of knowledge, experiences and best practices creating a community of knowledge in Digital Health globally.	https://echalliance.com/
PCHalliance	a membership-based HIMSS Innovation Company, accelerates technical, business and social strategies necessary to advance personal connected health and is committed to improving health behaviors and chronic disease management via connected health technologies. The Personal Connected Health Alliance (PCHalliance) is working to advance patient/consumer-centered health, wellness and disease prevention. The Alliance mobilizes a coalition of stakeholders to realize the full potential of personal connected health. PCHalliance members are a vibrant ecosystem of technology and life sciences industry icons and innovative, early stage companies along with governments, academic institutions, and associations from around the world.	https://www.pchalliance.org

5G Health Association	The fifth generation (5G) mobile communications standard is a new technology that enables a multitude of innovative applications in all areas of daily life. One of the essential areas for citizens is the health sector.	https://5g-health.org/
World Health Organization (WHO)	The World Health Organization (WHO) is a specialized agency of the United Nations responsible for international public health. The WHO Constitution, which establishes the agency's governing structure and principles, states its main objective as "the attainment by all peoples of the highest possible level of health". It is headquartered in Geneva, Switzerland, with six semi-autonomous regional offices and 150 field offices worldwide.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/World_Health_Organization
5G to go	Based in Erlangen-Tennenlohe, was founded in 2019 as part of the "5G Bavaria" initiative of the Fraunhofer Institute for Integrated Circuits IIS and is a 100% subsidiary of LZE GmbH. We support our partners in planning, building and operating generally available 5G campus networks and making them available to customers for 5G tests.	https://5gtogo.de/
European Association for logistics and transport in Healthcare	Ealth.org is an organisation that represents the interests of companies involved in the healthcare product supply chain in Europe.	http://www.ealth.org/
EU4Health	EU4Health is the EU's ambitious response to COVID-19. The pandemic has a major impact on patients, medical and healthcare staff, and health systems in Europe. The new EU4Health programme will go beyond crisis response to address healthcare systems' resilience.	https://ec.europa.eu/health/funding/eu4health_en
EIT Health	<i>EIT Health</i> is a network of best-in-class health innovators backed by the EU. We deliver solutions to enable European citizens to live longer, healthier lives.	https://eithealth.eu/
Energy		
EUTC	European Utilities Telecom Council (EUTC)	https://eutc.org/
EDSO	European Distribution System Operators for Smart Grids	https://www.edsoforsmartgrids.eu/
FEDARENE	European Federation of Agencies and Regions for Energy and the Environment is the premier European network of regional and local organisations which implement, coordinate and facilitate energy and environment policies. Regional and local agencies, regional governments and departments working in these fields, are represented in FEDARENE.	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/FEDARENE
ETIP	Smart Networks for Energy Transition	https://www.etip-snet.eu
EIT InnoEnergy	EIT InnoEnergy is spearheading the way to a decarbonised Europe by 2050 through the leadership of three industrial alliances: battery storage, green hydrogen and solar photovoltaics.	https://www.innoenergy.com/
Industry/Manufacturing		
5GACIA	5G-ACIA is a global forum for shaping 5G in the industrial domain. The paramount objective of 5G-ACIA is to ensure the best possible applicability of 5G technology for connected industries, in particular the manufacturing and process industries.	https://www.5g-acia.org/
IIC	The Industrial Internet Consortium (IIC) is a not-for-profit partnership of industry, government and academia. It was founded in March 2014 to bring together the	https://www.iiconsortium.org/

	<p>organizations and technologies necessary to accelerate the growth of the industrial internet by identifying, assembling, testing and promoting best practices. Members work collaboratively to speed the commercial use of advanced technologies. Membership includes small and large technology innovators, vertical market leaders, researchers, universities and government organizations. The resources of the IIC give organizations the guidance needed to strategically apply digital technologies and achieve digital transformation.</p>	
EFFRA	<p>The European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA) is a non-for-profit, industry-driven association promoting the development of new and innovative production technologies. It was the official representative of the private side in the Factories of the Future public-private partnership and nowadays of the Made in Europe partnership under the newest European framework programme "Horizon Europe".</p>	https://www.effra.eu/efra
ETP	<p>European Technology Platform for the Future of Textiles and Clothing.</p>	https://www.textile-platform.eu/
euRobotics	<p>euRobotics aisbl (Association Internationale Sans But Lucratif) is a Brussels based international non-profit association for all stakeholders in European robotics. It was founded in September 2012 with the aim to strengthen Europe's competitiveness and to ensure industrial leadership of manufacturers, providers and end-users of robotics technology-based systems and services. The objectives of euRobotics are to boost European robotics research, development and innovation and to foster a positive perception of robotics.</p>	https://www.eu-robotics.net/eurobotics/about/index.php?idart=29
Maritime		
IALA	<p>The International Association of Marine Aids to Navigation and Lighthouse Authorities (IALA), previously known as International Association of Lighthouse Authorities, is an intergovernmental organization founded in 1957 to collect and provide nautical expertise and advice. IALA is also known by its French name of Association Internationale de Signalisation Maritime (AISM).</p>	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/International_Association_of_Marine_Aids_to_Navigation_and_Lighthouse_Authorities
Agriculture		
European Environment Agency	<p>European Environment Agency: is an agency of the European Union, whose task is to provide sound, independent information on the environment. The EEA aims to support sustainable development by helping to achieve significant and measurable improvement in Europe's environment, through the provision of timely, targeted, relevant and reliable information to policymaking agents and the public.</p> <p>AIOTI. In relation with Smart Farming and Food Security.</p>	https://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/agriculture/intro
SmartAgriHubs	<p>SmartAgriHubs is a €20 M EU project under the Horizon 2020 instrument, and brings together a consortium of well over 164 partners in the European agri-food sector. The project aims to realise the digitisation of European agriculture by fostering an agricultural innovation ecosystem dedicated to excellence, sustainability and success.</p>	https://www.smartagrihubs.eu/about
agROBOfood	<p>The agROBOfood project, a consortium of 39 partners aims to accelerate the sector's digital transformation through the adoption of robotic technologies. To boost the uptake of robotic solutions, it will establish a sustainable network of digital innovation hubs (DIHs). At the heart of the project are innovation experiments (IEs) that will be organised and monitored by the DIHs. The European robotics community will be involved throughout the project to ensure maximum</p>	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/825395

	synergy. This will maximise the return of investments from the digital transformation of agri-food.	
Projects		
Mobility		
5GENESIS	the main goal of 5GENESIS will be to validate 5G KPIs for various 5G use cases, in both controlled set-ups and large-scale events. This will be achieved by bringing together results from a considerable number of EU projects as well as the partners' internal R&D activities in order to realise an integrated End-to-end 5G Facility.	https://5genesis.eu/
5G VINNI	The 5G-VINNI concept is to develop an (E2E 5G facility that can be used to first demonstrate the practical implementation of infrastructure to support the key 5G KPIs, and then to allow vertical industries to test and validate specific applications that are dependent upon those KPIs.	https://www.5g-vinni.eu
5G!DRONES	5G!Drones aim is to trial several UAV use-cases covering eMBB, URLLC, and mMTC 5G services, and to validate 5G KPIs for supporting such challenging use-cases. The project will drive the UAV verticals and 5G networks to a win-win position, on one hand by showing that 5G is able to guarantee UAV vertical KPIs, and on the other hand by demonstrating that 5G can support challenging use-cases that put pressure on network resources, such as low-latency and reliable communication, massive number of connections and high bandwidth requirements, simultaneously. 5G!DRONES will build on top of the 5G facilities provided by the ICT-17 projects and a number of support sites, while identifying and developing the missing components to trial UAV use-cases.	https://5gdrones.eu
5GROWTH	Its aim is to empower vertical industries such as Industry 4.0, Transportation, and Energy with Artificial Intelligence-driven automated 5G end-to-end solutions that will allow them to simultaneously achieve their respective key performance targets.	https://5growth.eu/
5G-HEART	5G-HEART (validation trials) focuses on these vital vertical use-cases of healthcare, transport and aquaculture. In the health area, 5G-HEART will validate pillcams for automatic detection in screening of colon cancer and vital-sign patches with advanced geo-localization as well as 5G AR/VR paramedic services. In the transport area, 5G-HEART will validate autonomous/assisted/remote driving and vehicle data services. Regarding food, focus will be on 5G-based transformation of the aquaculture sector (worldwide importance for Norway, Greece, Ireland).	https://5gheart.org/
5G TOURS	The goal of 5G-TOURS is to get the European 5G Vision of “5G empowering vertical industries” [5GPPP16] closer to commercial deployment with highly innovative use cases involving cross-industry partnerships.	https://5gtours.eu/
5G VICTORI	5G solutions for verticals is a well-defined European objective. This requires developing 5G infrastructures to address a wide range of applications adopting flexible architectures, offering converged services across heterogeneous technology domains with unified software control. However, vertical industries today can only verify use cases in small scales in commercial environments, before investing in large scale deployments.	https://www.5g-victori-project.eu
5GCroCo	5GCroCo will trial 5G technologies in the cross-border corridor along France, Germany and Luxembourg. In addition, 5GCroCo also aims at defining new business models that can be built on top of this unprecedented connectivity and service provisioning capacity. Ultimately, 5GCroCo will impact relevant standardization bodies from the telco and automotive industries.	https://5gcroco.eu/

5G-CARMEN	The key innovations are centred around developing an autonomously managed hybrid network, combining direct short range V2V (vehicle to vehicle) and V2I (vehicle to infrastructure) communications with long-range V2N (vehicle to network) communications.	https://5gcarmen.eu/about/
5G-MOBIX	5G-MOBIX will develop and test automated vehicle functionalities using 5G core technological innovations along multiple cross-border corridors and urban trial sites, under conditions of vehicular traffic, network coverage, service demand, as well as considering the inherently distinct legal, business and social local aspects.	https://www.5g-mobix.com/
5GMed	5GMed will demonstrate advanced Cooperative Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) and Future Railway Mobile Communications System services (FRMCS) along the “Figueres – Perpignan” cross-border corridor between Spain and France. Enabled by a multi-stakeholder compute and network infrastructure deployed by MNOs, neutral hosts, and road and rail operators, based on 5G and offering support for AI functions.	https://5g-ppp.eu/5gmed/
5G-Blueprint	G-Blueprint envisions to design and validate a technical architecture and a business and governance model for uninterrupted cross-border teleoperated transport based on 5G connectivity.	https://www.5gblueprint.eu/
5G-Routes	The 5G-ROUTES technical approach is based on a modular architecture in which the various 5G CAM technological enablers are integrated via open interfaces and APIs. These enablers will facilitate the measurement and visualisation of 5G network and service-level KPIs of the use cases, in parallel, and in near real-time whilst exercised in the field, as well as benchmarking and access from multiple locations.	https://www.5g-routes.eu
5GMETA	The 5GMETA open platform aims to leverage car-captured data to stimulate, facilitate and feed with them innovative products and services. By expanding 5G network functions, 5GMETA will stimulate and facilitate innovative products and services whilst ensuring data	https://5gmeta-project.eu/
AutoDrive	will provide fail-aware, fail-safe, and fail-operational integrated electronic components, Electrical/Electronic (E/E) architectures as well as (deeply) embedded software systems for highly and fully automated driving to make future mobility safer, more efficient, affordable, and end-user acceptable. Advancing towards fail-operational systems will require increased reliability and availability of components, new redundancy schemes as well as architectures, and methodologies to appropriately manage and balance complexity, cost, robustness, and flexibility.	https://autodrive-project.eu/
SECRETAS	is to develop software for validating architecting methodologies, reference architectures, components and suitable integration, as well as verification approaches for automated systems in different domains. These will combine high security and privacy protection while preserving functional-safety and operational performance. SECRETAS will take a first important step to developing and enhancing trustworthiness, particularly for the future European transportation and medical industries.	https://secretas-project.eu/
TrustVehicle	Automated driving can be implemented with relatively simple controllers if the current location of the ego vehicle and the current and future locations of other road users are known without uncertainty. However, this is not going to happen in the initial stages of the introduction of automated driving systems into the	https://www.mobility.eu/projects/brave-interact-trustvehicle-project-cluster

	<p>market. As a consequence, system and human driver uncertainty pose a significant challenge in the development of trustable and fault-tolerant automated driving controllers, especially for conditional automation (SAE level 3) in mixed traffic scenarios.</p>	
<p>BRAVE</p>	<p>Based on existing prototypes of automated vehicles (provided by the consortium), multidisciplinary research will be performed to ensure the needs of the users (drivers), other road users (other drivers and Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs)), and the perspectives of stakeholders (driving instructors, insurance companies, authorities, certifiers, policy makers and regulators), as a key for obtaining viable and market-ready products.</p>	<p>https://www.mobility.eu/projects/brave-interact-trustvehicle-project-cluster</p>
<p>New Control</p>	<p>NewControl will develop and deliver virtualized platforms for each vehicular subsystem essential to autonomous operation at SAE Level 3+. Each of these unifies the critical components required to realize a specific function – perception, cognition, control – through vertical integration within an adaptive (not rigid) architectural framework. The resulting virtual platforms effectively deliver specific functionalities as services to the vehicular platform, abstracting internal implementation, enabling portability to different application domains, and facilitating modular development of automation that is guaranteed as safe by design.</p>	<p>https://www.newcontrol-project.eu/</p>
<p>PRYSTINE</p>	<p>Among the actual trends that will affect society in the coming years, autonomous driving stands out as having the potential to disruptively change the automotive industry as we know it today. As a consequence, this will also highly impact the semiconductor industry and open new market opportunities, since semiconductors play an indispensable role as enablers for automated vehicles. Fully automated driving has been identified as one major enabler to master the Grand Societal Challenges of safe, clean, and efficient mobility. For this, fail-operational behavior is essential in the sense, plan, and act stages of the automation chain in order to handle safety-critical situations by its own, which currently is not reached with state-of-the-art approaches also due to missing reliable environment perception and sensor fusion.</p>	<p>https://prystine.eu/</p>
<p>AI4CSM</p>	<p>Develop the functional architectures for next generation ECAS vehicles based on ECS, embedded intelligence and functional virtualization for connected and shared mobility using trustworthy AI. This mission applies on different mobility sectors, including the automotive and semiconductor sector as well as the society.</p>	<p>https://ai4csm.automotive.oth-aw.de/index.php</p>
<p>ADACORSA</p>	<p>Provides European technology to render drones as a safe and efficient component of the mobility mix, with differentiated, safe and reliable capabilities in extended beyond visual line of sight (BVLOS) operations.</p>	<p>https://adacorsa.eu/</p>
<p>interACT</p>	<p>INTERACT is an infrastructure project under the auspices of SCANNET, a circumarctic network of currently 89 terrestrial field bases in northern Europe, Russia, US, Canada, Greenland, Iceland, the Faroe Islands and Scotland as well as stations in northern alpine areas. INTERACT specifically seeks to build capacity for research and monitoring all over the Arctic, and is offering access to numerous research stations through the Transnational Access Program.</p>	<p>https://eu-interact.org/</p>
<p>InsectT</p>	<p>The project features a big variety of industry-driven use cases embedded into various application domains where Europe is in a leading position, i.e. smart infrastructure, building, manufacturing, automotive, aeronautics, railway, urban public transport, maritime as well as health.</p>	<p>http://www.insectt.mind-net.eu/</p>
<p>Media</p>		

5GENESIS	The main goal of 5GENESIS will be to validate 5G KPIs for various 5G use cases, in both controlled set-ups and large-scale events. This will be achieved by bringing together results from a considerable number of EU projects as well as the partners' internal R&D activities in order to realise an integrated End-to-end 5G Facility.	https://5genesis.eu/
5G EVE	5G EVE is the European 5G validation platform for extensive trials. It is one of three 5G PPP infrastructure projects started on 1st July 2018. The goal is to implement and test advanced 5G infrastructures in Europe. The 5G-EVE concept is based on further developing and interconnecting existing European sites in Greece, Spain, France, and Italy to form a unique 5G end-to-end facility.	https://www.5g-eve.eu/
5G!DRONES	5G!Drones aim is to trial several UAV use-cases covering eMBB, URLLC, and mMTC 5G services, and to validate 5G KPIs for supporting such challenging use-cases. The project will drive the UAV verticals and 5G networks to a win-win position, on one hand by showing that 5G is able to guarantee UAV vertical KPIs, and on the other hand by demonstrating that 5G can support challenging use-cases that put pressure on network resources, such as low-latency and reliable communication, massive number of connections and high bandwidth requirements, simultaneously. 5G!DRONES will build on top of the 5G facilities provided by the ICT-17 projects and a number of support sites, while identifying and developing the missing components to trial UAV use-cases.	https://5gdrones.eu
5G Solutions	The 5G-SOLUTIONS main project objective is to conduct advanced field trials of innovative and thematically diverse digital services that require 5G capabilities and performance in the vertical domains of Factories of the Future, Smart Energy, Smart Cities, Smart Ports and Media & Entertainment, directly engaging with end-user actors, so as to validate the technological performance of 5G technology in successfully serving them, as well as validate the business models and potential of these use cases prior to commercial deployment.	https://5gsolutionsproject.eu/about/objectives/
5G TOURS	The goal of 5G-TOURS is to get the European 5G Vision of “5G empowering vertical industries” [5GPPP16] closer to commercial deployment with highly innovative use cases involving cross-industry partnerships.	http://5gtours.eu/
5G-VICTORI	5G solutions for verticals is a well-defined European objective. This requires developing 5G infrastructures to address a wide range of applications adopting flexible architectures, offering converged services across heterogeneous technology domains with unified software control. However, vertical industries today can only verify use cases in small scales in commercial environments, before investing in large scale deployments.	https://www.5g-victori-project.eu/about-5g-victori/
5GRecords	The key challenge of 5G-RECORDS is to explore the possibilities that new hardware devices and technologies may bring to the 5G ecosystem.	https://www.5g-records.eu/
Stars4Media	Stars4Media is an innovation exchange programme aiming at facilitating cooperation between media professionals, to accelerate media innovation and cross-border cooperation. Media professionals, media organisations and tech companies from EU countries have the chance to cooperate around bottom-up Initiatives to test ideas and technologies, develop new business models and produce journalistic content.	https://stars4media.eu/
Manufacturing		
5G SMART	To further accelerate take-up of 5G in the manufacturing ecosystem, 5G-SMART will explore the roles of mobile network operators and new business models. 5G-SMART will result in development of future 5G standards for the manufactur-	https://5gsmart.eu

	ing sector complemented by new 5G enabled manufacturing products and solutions. 5G-SMART open days will directly address small and medium enterprises making 5G-SMART technology accessible to them. 5G-SMART lead by Ericsson brings together a strong consortium of partners involved in every aspect of the manufacturing ecosystem.	
Health & Wellbeing		
5G EVE	5G EVE is the European 5G validation platform for extensive trials. It is one of three 5G PPP infrastructure projects started on 1st July 2018. The goal is to implement and test advanced 5G infrastructures in Europe. The 5G-EVE concept is based on further developing and interconnecting existing European sites in Greece, Spain, France, and Italy to form a unique 5G end-to-end facility.	https://www.5g-eve.eu/
5G HEART	5G-HEART (validation trials) focuses on these vital vertical use-cases of healthcare, transport and aquaculture. In the health area, 5G-HEART will validate pillcams for automatic detection in screening of colon cancer and vital-sign patches with advanced geo-localization as well as 5G AR/VR paramedic services. In the transport area, 5G-HEART will validate autonomous/assisted/remote driving and vehicle data services. Regarding food, focus will be on 5G-based transformation of aquaculture sector (worldwide importance for Norway, Greece, Ireland).	https://5gheart.org/
5G TOURS	The goal of 5G-TOURS is to get the European 5G Vision of “5G empowering vertical industries” [5GPPP16] closer to commercial deployment with highly innovative use cases involving cross-industry partnerships.	https://5gtours.eu/
5G research for rural health care	It is the objective of the project 5G4Healthcare to establish a platform based on 5G technology that enables testing and evaluation of digital applications in scenarios of rural healthcare in living labs (real environments) and test beds.	https://5gheart.org
Health5G	It brings together the experience related to 5G network technologies, eHealth service providers, medical device manufacturers, security experts and medical experts as end users, and capabilities required to achieve the project objectives and especially to push the new technologies and innovations issued from the project efficiently towards the market.	http://health5g.eu/
MOMENTUM - Mobile medical 5G-technology for emergency care	In the MOMENTUM project, medical technology is being developed that can be used not only in the hospital (eg in the trauma room, operating theater, intensive care unit), but also in preclinical care at the scene of the accident and in the ambulance.	https://www.ic-cas.de/projekte/momentum/?lang=en
Energy		
5G EVE	5G EVE is the European 5G validation platform for extensive trials. It is one of three 5G PPP infrastructure projects started on 1st July 2018. The goal is to implement and test advanced 5G infrastructures in Europe. The 5G-EVE concept is based on further developing and interconnecting existing European sites in Greece, Spain, France, and Italy to form a unique 5G end-to-end facility.	https://www.5g-eve.eu/
5G VINNI	The 5G-VINNI concept is to develop an (E2E 5G facility that can be used to first demonstrate the practical implementation of infrastructure to support the key 5G KPIs, and then to allow vertical industries to test and validate specific applications that are dependent upon those KPIs.	https://www.5g-vinni.eu

5G GROWTH	The vision of the 5Growth project is to empower verticals industries such as Industry 4.0, Transportation, and Energy with an AI-driven Automated and Shareable 5G End-to-End Solution that will allow these industries to achieve simultaneously their respective key performance targets.	https://5growth.eu/
5G SOLUTIONS	Provides the technological enablers for facilitating the execution of the field trials over specific ICT-17 5G facilities. A unified Cross-Domain Service Orchestration based on automation enabling multi-domain slicing and 5G service lifecycle automation. A smart KPI visualization system for automating the analysis and presentation of the results obtained from ICT-17 facilities and presenting them through an intuitive user-friendly dashboard in graphical form in near real time. A set of open-standards easy-to-use intent-based APIs, including application APIs for facilitating the development, portability, provisioning of and interactions with new user-friendly applications and solutions that require 5G capabilities by SMEs and/or vertical specific systems.	https://5gsolutionsproject.eu/
5G VICTORI	5G solutions for verticals is a well-defined European objective. This requires developing 5G infrastructures to address a wide range of applications adopting flexible architectures, offering converged services across heterogeneous technology domains with unified software control. However, vertical industries today can only verify use cases in small scales in commercial environments, before investing in large scale deployments.	https://www.5g-victori-project.eu
Logistics		
5GLOGINNOV	5G-LOGINNOV's vision is to optimise freight and traffic operations at ports and logistics hubs by using new innovative concepts, applications and devices supported by 5G technologies, Internet of Things (IoT), data analytics, next generation traffic management, Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) and the 5G logistics corridor.	https://5g-loginnov.eu/
Vertical trials		
5G-EPICENTRE (security/PPDR)	5G-EPICENTRE will deliver an open end-to-end experimentation 5G platform focusing on software solutions that serve the needs of PPDR.	https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-epicentre/
5GMediaHub (media)	5GMediaHUB aims to help EU to achieve the goal of becoming a world leader in 5G, by accelerating the testing and validation of innovative 5G-empowered media applications and NetApps from 3rd party experimenters and NetApps developers, through an open, integrated and fully featured Experimentation Facility. This will significantly reduce not only the service creation lifecycle but also the time to market barrier, thus providing such actors that are primarily from SMEs, with a competitive advantage against their rivals outside EU. In particular, 5GMediaHUB will build and operate an elastic, secure and trusted multi-tenant service execution and NetApps development environment based on an open cloud-based architecture and APIs, by developing and integrating a testing and validation system with two existing well-established 5G testbeds (by CTTC and 5G-VIVVI by Telenor) for enabling the fast prototyping, testing and validation of novel 5G services and NetApps.	https://www.5gmediahub.eu
5G-INDUCE (industry 4.0)	5G-INDUCE targets the development of an open, ETSI NFV compatible, 5G orchestration platform for the deployment of advanced 5G NetApps. The platform's unique features provide the capability to the NetApp developers to define and modify the application requirements, while the underlay intelligent OSS can expose the network capabilities to the end users on the application level without revealing any infrastructure related information. This process enables an application-oriented network management and optimization approach that is in line	https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-induce/

	with the operator’s role as manager of its own facilities, while it offers the development framework environment to any developer and service provider through which tailor-made applications can be designed and deployed, for the benefit of vertical industries and without any indirect dependency through a cloud provider.	
5G-IANA	5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third party experimenters (i.e., SMEs) in the Automotive-related 5G-PPP vertical will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. An Automotive Open Experimental Platform (AOEP) will be specified, as the whole set of hardware and software resources that provides the compute and communication/transport infrastructure as well as the management and orchestration components, coupled with an enhanced NetApp Toolkit tailored to the Automotive sector. 5G-IANA will expose to experimenters secured and standardized APIs for facilitating all the different steps towards the production stage of a new service. 5G-IANA will target different virtualization technologies integrating different MANO frameworks for enabling the deployment of the end-to-end network services across different domains (vehicles, road infrastructure, MEC nodes and cloud resources).	https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-iana/
5GCroCo	5GCroCo will trial 5G technologies in the cross-border corridor along France, Germany and Luxembourg. In addition, 5GCroCo also aims at defining new business models that can be built on top of this unprecedented connectivity and service provisioning capacity. Ultimately, 5GCroCo will impact relevant standardization bodies from the telco and automotive industries.	https://5gcroco.eu/
5G-CARMEN	The key innovations are centred around developing an autonomously managed hybrid network, combining direct short range V2V (vehicle to vehicle) and V2I (vehicle to infrastructure) communications with long-range V2N (vehicle to network) communications.	https://5gcarmen.eu/about/
5G-MOBIX	5G-MOBIX will develop and test automated vehicle functionalities using 5G core technological innovations along multiple cross-border corridors and urban trial sites, under conditions of vehicular traffic, network coverage, service demand, as well as considering the inherently distinct legal, business and social local aspects.	https://www.5g-mobix.com/
5G GROWTH	The vision of the 5GGrowth project is to empower vertical industries such as Industry 4.0, Transportation, and Energy with an AI-driven Automated and Shareable 5G End-to-End Solution that will allow these industries to achieve simultaneously their respective key performance targets.	https://5growth.eu/